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**LIF Investigation of the Mechanisms
Controlling Air-Water Mass Transfer
at a Free Interface**

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Summary

A laser-induced fluorescence (LIF) technique is described to measure two-dimensional vertical concentration profiles of gases in the aqueous mass boundary layer at a free water surface. The technique uses an acid-base reaction of the fluorescence indicator fluorescein at the water surface to visualize the concentration profiles. It is shown that this technique is capable of measuring the two-dimensional vertical concentration profiles at a rate of 200 frames per second with a spatial resolution of $20\ \mu\text{m}$. The results show that the decrease of the measured mean concentration profiles into the bulk is faster than predicted by the small eddy model. The measurements agree with the predictions of the surface renewal model. Combined experiments with a wave slope imaging technique reveal that there is no local correlation between wave slope and boundary layer thickness. The image sequences indicate that there is only a weak correlation between the occurrence of surface renewal phenomena and steep wave trains. Surface renewal effects for a fully developed wave field renew the fluid in the aqueous mass boundary layer up to the water surface. This is not true for the case of a flat interface. Here, the changes of the boundary layer thickness after a surface renewal event are significantly smaller.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

In the last 150 years the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere increased by 25%. In the same time span the average temperature increased by 0.5K. This so called global warming or green house effect is one of the reasons explaining the enlarged interest in understanding climatic cycles and natural processes. The oceans act as the major sink for CO₂. More than 90% of the total amount of global CO₂ is dissolved in the oceans. Many problems in understanding the role of the oceans on the global CO₂ budget still remain unsolved. The predictions for the annual input of CO₂ into the oceans differ significantly. If the smaller estimate is correct some 1.6 GtC have to vanish in some other sink. The most probable explanation is that this amount is absorbed by an increased plant growth due to the increased CO₂ concentration. Nevertheless this hypothesis is unproven. It is not even understood how an increase in CO₂ influences plant growth.

There are two bottlenecks for the transfer of gases into the ocean. The first is the transfer through the air-water phase boundary. It is found that this transfer is controlled by a microscopic layer at the water surface where the influence of the relatively slow molecular diffusion is bigger than the one of turbulent transport. The physical processes controlling this so called *mass boundary layer* are the subject of this thesis. The other bottleneck of gas transfer into the oceans is the deep water formation because only the upper 100 to 200 meters of the oceans are well mixed. Neither of these processes is fully understood yet.

Air blowing over a liquid surface greatly increases the rate of physical absorption of a gas. This increase is associated with the appearance of waves. The rate of a gas invading into the water is measured by the *transfer velocity*, which is defined as the velocity of a hypothetical gas column pushing into the water. By comparing the transfer velocities for equal values of momentum input by the wind into the water it becomes obvious that the presence of waves is a crucial factor. For conditions with an equal momentum input into the water, the transfer velocity changes by a factor of 5 if waves are present or not (fig. 1.1 shows measurements at the wind/wave facility of the University of Heidelberg).

Figure 1.1: *Transfer velocity of gas exchange between air and water measured at the circular wind/wave facility of the University of Heidelberg. Compare the exchange rates at $u_* = 0.95$ cm/s for a smooth and a wavy interface (from (Kandlbinder 1994)).*

At present the role of waves is not entirely understood. Different models try to explain the influence of waves but rule out each other in the underlying assumptions on the physical mechanisms. Unfortunately it is impossible for measurements that average over a larger area, i.e. mass transfer measurements, to distinguish between the current models. The interest in the mechanisms of gas exchange processes is not only of academic interest but also important for the parameterization of mass transfer in natural systems. The parameters known so far can only give good estimates of transfer rates for the two extreme wave conditions, i.e. for a completely flat and a perfectly wavy interface without any surfactants. Unfortunately in natural waters the presence of natural or man-made surface active films greatly influences the rate of gas exchange. Due to this uncertainty and the experimental difficulties for measuring transfer rates in the ocean the margins of error for estimates of gas transfer in natural waters range from 30% to a factor of two. An understanding of the transfer of mass between gas and water plays an important role in developing mathematical models for physical and chemical processes in the ocean. It is also important in understanding climatical, pollution and biochemical cycles.

The goal of this work is to investigate the mechanisms of air-water gas transfer with non-intrusive laser-induced fluorescence (LIF) techniques. These techniques provide a direct insight into the spatio-temporal structure of the gas concentration within the aqueous mass boundary layer.

The theoretical background and a derivation of the basic models is given in chapter 2. This

Figure 1.2: *Transfer velocity of gas exchange between air and water measured for different surfactant concentrations at the wind/wave channel of the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institute (from (Frew et al. 1995)).*

chapter also introduces the concept of concentration profiles. The physico-chemical principles for measuring concentration profiles in the aqueous mass boundary layer with LIF techniques are explained in chapter 3. Chapter 4 shows the experimental setup for the LIF techniques at two different wind/wave channels. A comparison of the measured results with results from parallel mass balance experiments is presented in chapter 5. Chapter 6 supplies the results and discussion for measurements at flat and wavy interfaces. Finally chapter 7 concludes these results and gives an outlook on future experiments.

Chapter 2

Theory of gas exchange

Except for conditions of stable stratification gas transfer between air and water is controlled by the interaction of molecular diffusion and turbulent transport. Turbulent transport is usually much more effective than molecular diffusion. Therefore in the bulk transport is mainly due to turbulence. Closer to the phase boundary in the mean the scale of the eddies has to decrease. For these smaller scales viscosity and buoyancy become the major damping terms. Directly at the water surface any turbulent transport has to vanish, as turbulence structures cannot penetrate the air-water phase boundary. Therefore molecular diffusion is the only transport mechanism across the water surface. This leads to the definition of the *aqueous mass boundary layer*, in which diffusive transport exceeds turbulent transport. In this layer turbulent transport has to increase from zero to its value in the bulk. For gases this layer is between 20 and 300 μm thick and controls the transfer of all non-reactive or slowly reacting gases.

Molecular diffusion is the process which causes a decrease of concentration differences. It is described by Fick's 1st and 2nd law. Fick's first law states that the flux density of the transported substance is in the opposite direction than the concentration gradient. The proportionality constant between the flux density, \mathbf{j} , and the concentration gradient is called the diffusivity, D :

$$\mathbf{j} = -D\nabla c. \quad (2.1)$$

For an unsteady diffusive transport Fick's 2nd law applies:

$$\frac{dc}{dt} = \frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}\nabla c = -\nabla\mathbf{j} = D\nabla^2 c, \quad (2.2)$$

where D is the diffusivity of the transported tracer. Fluid velocity is denoted by \mathbf{u} with Cartesian components $\{u, v, w\}$ in directions $\{x, y, z\}$. The flux through a unit area is expressed by \mathbf{j} . Equation 2.2 is linear in the concentration and the turbulent transport is included in the term $\mathbf{u}\nabla c$.

The linearity gives way to the definition of the *transfer velocity*, k , based on the empirical argument that the amount transferred is proportional to the concentration difference and the interfacial area.

Figure 2.1: *Definition of the coordinate system and nomenclature of the velocity components. The x coordinate lies in the stream-wise direction, the y coordinate in the cross-wise direction and the z coordinate in the vertical direction. The corresponding velocity components to x , y and z are named u , v , and w , respectively.*

Therefore k is defined to be equal to the flux density divided by the concentration difference, Δc , between the water surface and some reference depth ($\Delta c = c_{surface} - c_{bulk}$):

$$k = \frac{j}{\Delta c} \quad , \quad (2.3)$$

where $j = |\mathbf{j}|$. The turbulent velocity field is a solution of the Navier Stokes equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} = \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{u} + \frac{1}{\rho} \mathbf{F} - \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p \quad (2.4)$$

where ∇p stands for the pressure gradient, ρ is the fluid density, \mathbf{F} is the sum of the external forces, also called body forces. The viscous properties of the fluid are expressed by the kinematic viscosity, ν , which is defined as the ratio of the (Newtonian) viscosity, μ , to the fluid density, ρ : $\nu = \mu/\rho$. Except for the terms applied by the external forces and the pressure gradient this equation is the analogue to Fick's 2nd law replacing the concentration c by $\rho \mathbf{u}$. In contrast to equation 2.2, it is a non-linear partial differential equation in \mathbf{u} . The non-linearity arises from the dual role of the velocity in determining the acceleration of a fluid particle. A technique for dealing with equations 2.2 and 2.4 is a perturbation approach dividing the components into a mean and a fluctuating part (Reynold's approach):

$$\mathbf{u} = \bar{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{u}' \quad \text{and} \quad c = \bar{c} + c'$$

where the barred letters stand for the mean and the primed letters for the fluctuating part. The mean values are independent of the averaging time t . That is to say that averaging has to be long compared to the typical time constants of the system. This leads to the conclusion that the mean of the fluctuations is zero: $\bar{\mathbf{u}'} = 0$. Putting this into Fick's 2nd law leads to the averaged equation¹:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{c}}{\partial t} + \bar{\mathbf{u}} \nabla \bar{c} = -\nabla \bar{\mathbf{j}} = -\nabla (\langle c' \mathbf{u}' \rangle - D \nabla \bar{c}) \quad , \quad (2.5)$$

¹The averaging term $\langle c' \mathbf{u}' \rangle$ is derived by substituting $\mathbf{u} \nabla c = \nabla (\mathbf{u} c) - c \nabla \mathbf{u}$. The second term of the right hand side of this equation is zero due to the continuity equation for incompressible fluids: $\nabla \mathbf{u} = 0$

where \bar{j} is the sum of the average molecular diffusion and turbulent fluxes. The brackets $\langle \dots \rangle$ stand for the temporal mean of the variables between the brackets. Up to this point no assumptions about turbulence structures were made.

Due to the absence of turbulent transport through the phase boundary in the mean Fick's 1st law applies directly at the water surface:

$$j = -D \left. \frac{\partial \bar{c}}{\partial z} \right|_{z=0} \quad (2.6)$$

This is to say that the flux density can be calculated from the slope of the concentration profile at the water surface ($z = 0$) if the diffusion constant of the tracer is known. From eqs. 2.3 and 2.6 the boundary layer thickness, z_* , can be defined as:

$$z_* = \frac{\Delta \bar{c}}{-\left. \frac{\partial \bar{c}}{\partial z} \right|_{z=0}} = \frac{D \Delta \bar{c}}{j} = \frac{D}{k} \quad (2.7)$$

Figure 2.2: *Definition of the boundary layer thickness as the depth difference between the water surface and the intersection of the tangent to the concentration profile at the water surface with the bulk concentration.*

The characteristic time t_* for the transport of a gas tracer through the aqueous mass boundary layer is calculated from the ratio of the boundary layer thickness to the transfer velocity:

$$t_* = \frac{z_*}{k} = \frac{D}{k^2} \quad (2.8)$$

These three equations above assume though that there is absolutely no resistance to mass transfer in the gas, i.e. that the transport on the air side can get infinitely fast.

Allowing the simplification of a process that is horizontally homogeneous in the mean leads to the following differential equation for concentrations:

$$\bar{j} = - \left(D \frac{\partial \bar{c}}{\partial z} - \langle c'w' \rangle \right) \quad (2.9)$$

where z is the vertical axis and w' is the velocity component in this direction. The equivalent equation for the velocity field is called Reynolds equation:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial t} = \rho \left(\nu \frac{\partial^2 \bar{u}}{\partial z^2} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \langle u'w' \rangle \right) \quad (2.10)$$

with u , v and w standing for the velocity components in the stream-wise, cross-wise and vertical direction, respectively (see fig. 2.1).

The turbulent term in this equation $\langle u'w' \rangle$ is called Reynold's stress. For a stationary state the left hand side of equation 2.10 is zero and the equation can be integrated over z . The result is a constant momentum flux density in the z direction:

$$j_m = \rho \left(\nu \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial z} - \langle u'w' \rangle \right) =: \tau$$

where the term $\nu \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial z}$ describes the viscous transport and $\langle u'w' \rangle$ the turbulent transport. The momentum flux density j_m is per definition equal to the friction force at the water surface, τ . This leads to the definition of a measure for the surface friction that has the dimensions of a velocity, the so called friction velocity u_* :

$$u_*^2 = \frac{\tau}{\rho}, \quad (2.11)$$

which is therefore a measure for the momentum transfer into the liquid. In a turbulent flow the Reynolds stress can be expressed by putting

$$\tau_t = -\rho \langle u'w' \rangle = A_\tau \frac{d\bar{u}}{dy}, \quad (2.12)$$

where A_τ is the so called mixing coefficient, which is often called "eddy viscosity" (*Schlichting* 1979). Combining this with eq. 2.11 leads to another expression for the friction velocity:

$$u_*^2 = \langle u'w' \rangle. \quad (2.13)$$

This definition shows that u_* is a measure of the intensity of turbulent eddying and of the correlation which exists between the fluctuating velocity components in x and z direction (*Schlichting* 1979).

Molecular diffusion of momentum in water exceeds that of dissolved gases by three orders of magnitude. To compare the transfer of momentum with the transfer of a tracer a dimensionless parameter is defined: the Schmidt number Sc . The Schmidt number is defined as the ratio of the kinematic viscosity of the medium (water) ν to the molecular diffusion constant of the gas in the medium:

$$Sc = \frac{\nu}{D} \quad (2.14)$$

The term tracer includes here all gases, heat and momentum. For dissolved gases in water the Schmidt number ranges between 100 and 2000.

2.1 Gas exchange models

Modeling the exchange processes has to deal with the change of transport mechanisms from diffusion to turbulence. The simplest model that does this simply assumes that there is a stagnant film with only diffusion. Below this film turbulent transport abruptly sets in. The other models are more sophisticated in their approach to model the change from diffusive to turbulent transport. Obviously diffusive transport is described by Fick's law but turbulent transport is described by the term $\langle c'w' \rangle$ in eq. 2.9. Gas exchange models try to find a simpler, i.e. mathematically solvable representation for $\langle c'w' \rangle$. This is done by introducing additional terms to the simple film model.

2.1.1 Film Model

Before dealing with the more elaborate models a closer look at the film model is helpful. This simplest theory for interfacial mass transfer assumes that the transport through the phase boundary can be divided into pure molecular diffusion through a stagnant film down to the boundary layer thickness z_* and pure turbulent transport below this depth. Fig. 2.3 shows a schematic view of this model.

Figure 2.3: *The film theory for mass transfer. The interfacial region is idealized as a hypothetical "unstirred layer". Mass transfer involves diffusion across this thin film. Note that the constant pressure value p_0 implies no resistance to mass transfer in the gas. (after (Cussler 1984))*

This is illustrated by the *Gedankenexperiment* that flow in the boundary layer is laminar down to a certain depth when the flow has to become turbulent. This is almost always hypothetical for fluid motions commonly occur right up to even a solid interface (Campbell and Hanratty 1982). Diffusion of a gas through a layer without any turbulence causes a direct proportionality of the transfer velocity k to the diffusivity D :

$$k = \frac{D}{z_*} \quad (2.15)$$

This prediction is obviously contradicted by experiments, which show a dependency of transfer velocity on diffusivity with an exponent that is smaller than 1: $k \propto D^n$ with $n < 1$. Pure diffusion through the boundary layer would also cause a linear concentration profile in the boundary layer.

2.1.2 Small eddy model

In this model the turbulent mass flux is parameterized with the aid of a turbulent diffusivity coefficient K_t . This coefficient naturally depends on z and the hydrodynamic conditions and becomes zero at the interface itself (cf. e.g. (Deacon 1977) and (Coantic 1986)). The physical picture behind these assumptions is to describe the turbulent flux through the boundary layer as a cascade of growing eddies. A mathematically sound procedure for calculating $K_t(z)$, is given by (Coantic 1986). It is shown here in detail to reveal the basic postulates and constraints that go into this model.

If the concentration fluctuations can be considered small compared to the mean concentrations a Taylor series expansion of $\bar{c}(z)$ around $z = 0$ is possible:

$$\bar{c}(z) = \bar{c}(0) + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{i!} \left. \frac{\partial^i \bar{c}}{\partial z^i} \right|_{z=0} z^i \quad (2.16)$$

At the water surface Fick's 1st law is valid and therefore for a stationary state eq. 2.6 applies:

$$D \left. \frac{\partial \bar{c}}{\partial z} \right|_{z=0} = -j. \quad (2.17)$$

For a stationary state successive derivatives of eq. 2.9 at $z = 0$ yield:

$$D \left. \frac{\partial^2 \bar{c}}{\partial z^2} \right|_{z=0} = \left. \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \langle c' w' \rangle \right|_{z=0} = \left(\langle w' \frac{\partial c'}{\partial z} \rangle + \langle c' \frac{\partial w'}{\partial z} \rangle \right) = 0 \Big|_{z=0}, \quad (2.18)$$

$$D \left. \frac{\partial^3 \bar{c}}{\partial z^3} \right|_{z=0} = \left. \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \langle c' w' \rangle \right|_{z=0} = \left(\underbrace{\langle w' \frac{\partial^2 c'}{\partial z^2} \rangle}_{=0} + 2 \underbrace{\langle \frac{\partial w'}{\partial z} \frac{\partial c'}{\partial z} \rangle}_{\equiv \alpha_3} + \underbrace{\langle c' \frac{\partial^2 w'}{\partial z^2} \rangle}_{=0} \right) \Big|_{z=0}, \quad (2.19)$$

$$\begin{aligned} D \left. \frac{\partial^4 \bar{c}}{\partial z^4} \right|_{z=0} &= \left. \frac{\partial^3}{\partial z^3} \langle c' w' \rangle \right|_{z=0} \\ &= \left(\underbrace{\langle c' \frac{\partial^3 w'}{\partial z^3} \rangle}_{=0} + 3 \underbrace{\langle \frac{\partial c'}{\partial z} \frac{\partial^2 w'}{\partial z^2} \rangle}_{\equiv \alpha_4} + 3 \underbrace{\langle \frac{\partial^2 c'}{\partial z^2} \frac{\partial w'}{\partial z} \rangle}_{\equiv \beta_4} + \underbrace{\langle c' \frac{\partial^2 w'}{\partial z^2} \rangle}_{=0} \right) \Big|_{z=0}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.20)$$

Boundary conditions

1. *rigid interface*: It is observed that the fluid immediately next to the interface, i.e. at the "walls", remains at rest. This is called the no slip condition which yields that all velocity fluctuations have to vanish at the interface (see fig. 2.4):

$$u'_0 = v'_0 = w'_0 = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad z = 0. \quad (2.21)$$

The continuity equation for an incompressible fluid

$$\frac{\partial u'}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v'}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w'}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (2.22)$$

leads to:

$$\left. \frac{\partial w'}{\partial z} \right|_{z=0} = 0. \quad (2.23)$$

Figure 2.4: *Universal dimensionless profiles of the intensity of fluctuation of the three velocity components in a flow close to a smooth wall according to the data by (Klebanoff 1955) (crosses) and (Laufer 1954) (circles). (from (Monin and Yaglom 1973))*

For the concentration field

$$c'_0 = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad z = 0 \quad (2.24)$$

is assumed in analogy to $u' = 0$ (Coantic 1986).

2. *mobile interface*: Only the normal velocity component w' has to be zero, while u' and v' can be different from zero at the interface, so that condition 2.21 reduces to

$$w'_0 = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad z = 0. \quad (2.25)$$

The continuity equation now gives

$$\left. \frac{\partial w'}{\partial z} \right|_{z=0} = - \left(\left. \frac{\partial u'}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v'}{\partial y} \right) \right|_{z=0} \neq 0 \quad (2.26)$$

The condition $c' = 0$ at $z = 0$ is still considered valid.

The boundary conditions for a **rigid wall** yield a nonzero value only for eq. 2.20, where the term α_4 is nonzero at $z = 0$. The Taylor expansion can then be written as:

$$\bar{c}(z) = \bar{c}(0) - \underbrace{\frac{j}{D}z}_{\text{diffusion}} + 0 + \underbrace{0 + \frac{1}{4!} \frac{z^4}{D} \alpha_4 + \text{higher order terms}}_{\text{turbulent transport}} \quad (2.27)$$

Replacing the turbulent transport term $\langle c'w' \rangle$ in eq. 2.9 with a depth dependent turbulent diffusion coefficient $K_t \frac{\partial \bar{c}}{\partial z}$ we get:

$$j = - (D + K_t(z)) \frac{\partial \bar{c}}{\partial z} \Rightarrow K_t = D - \frac{j}{\frac{\partial \bar{c}}{\partial z}}. \quad (2.28)$$

Taking the derivative with respect to z of the concentration in eq. 2.27 K_t gives:

$$K_t = D \left(1 - \frac{j}{j - \frac{1}{6} \alpha_4 z^3 + \text{higher order terms}} \right) \quad (2.29)$$

Finally in the immediate vicinity of a rigid smooth wall, i.e. for small z , eq. 2.29 can be approximated by a power series of the form:

$$(1 - x)^{-1} \approx 1 + \frac{1}{2}x + x^2 + \dots,$$

which yields

$$K_t = \tilde{\alpha} z^3 + \dots \quad \text{with} \quad \tilde{\alpha} = \frac{D \alpha_4}{12 j} \quad (2.30)$$

Next to a **free interface** the boundary conditions give non-zero values for the term α_3 in eq. 2.20. Thus the Taylor expansion is of the form:

$$\bar{c}(z) = \bar{c}(0) - \underbrace{\frac{j}{D}z}_{\text{diffusion}} + 0 + \underbrace{\frac{1}{3!} \frac{z^3}{D} \alpha_3 + \text{higher order terms}}_{\text{turbulent transport}}. \quad (2.31)$$

The terms of order z^4 and higher can be neglected compared to those of order z^4 . Thus we obtain:

$$K_t = D \left(1 + \frac{j}{j - 1/2 \alpha_3 z^2 + \text{higher order terms}} \right). \quad (2.32)$$

In the immediate vicinity of a free interface K_t is of the form:

$$K_t = \tilde{\alpha} z^2 + \dots \quad \text{with} \quad \tilde{\alpha} = \frac{D \alpha_3}{4j} \quad (2.33)$$

In order to compare different conditions the following dimensionless parameters are introduced, with the above terms substituted for $\langle c'w' \rangle$ in eq. 2.9:

$$z_+ = \frac{z}{z_*}, \quad t_+ = t/t_*, \quad \bar{c}_+ = \frac{\bar{c}}{\Delta \bar{c}}. \quad (2.34)$$

Using eqs. 2.30 and 2.33 this leads to a slightly different form of eq. 2.9:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{c}_+}{\partial t_+} = \frac{Dt_*}{z_*^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial z_+} \left[\left(1 + \frac{\alpha_m z_*^m}{D} z_+^m \right) \frac{\partial \bar{c}_+}{\partial z_+} \right]. \quad (2.35)$$

where the exponent m can be 2 or 3 depending on the boundary conditions for a mobile interface or a rigid wall, respectively. Together with equations 2.7 and 2.8 it can be seen that $\frac{Dt_*}{z_*^2} = 1$. In the same manner α_{m+} is defined as $\frac{\alpha_m z_*^m}{D}$:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{c}_+}{\partial t_+} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z_+} \left[(1 + \alpha_{m+} z_+^m) \frac{\partial \bar{c}_+}{\partial z_+} \right], \quad (2.36)$$

which can be integrated directly for a stationary state. Using the above boundary conditions in partial integration this leads to the dimensionless mean concentration profile for the small eddy model:

$$\bar{c}_+(z_+) \Big|_{z_+=0} = 0 \quad (2.37)$$

α_{m+} has to fulfill the boundary condition

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{1}{1 + \alpha_{m+} z_+^m} dz_+ = 1, \quad (2.38)$$

which leads to the condition for α_{m+} :

$$\alpha_{m+} = \left(\frac{\pi}{m \sin(\pi/m)} \right)^m. \quad (2.39)$$

For the case of $m = 2$ this leads to the equation for the concentration profile:

$$\bar{c}_+(z_+) = \frac{2}{\pi} \operatorname{arccot} \left(\frac{\pi}{2} z_+ \right). \quad (2.40)$$

For the case of $m = 3$ the following equation can be deduced:

$$\bar{c}_+(z_+) = \left[1 + \frac{-6 \arctan(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}) + 2\sqrt{3} \log(9) - \sqrt{3} \log(81)}{4\pi} - \frac{6 \arctan(\frac{-3^{\frac{3}{2}} + 4\pi z}{9}) + 2\sqrt{3} \log(9 + 2\sqrt{3}\pi z)}{4\pi} - \frac{\sqrt{3} \log(81 - 2 \cdot 3^{\frac{5}{2}} \pi z + 12 \pi^2 z^2)}{4\pi} \right] \quad (2.41)$$

Figure 2.5 shows both cases in a plot with dimensionless variables (grey curves).

Figure 2.5: Comparison of the mean concentration profiles predicted by the surface renewal (black curves) and the small eddy model (grey curves). For both models the curves for Schmidt number exponents $n = 1/2$ and $n = 2/3$ are plotted. The larger scale turbulence postulated by the surface renewal model gives way to a faster decrease of mean concentration into the bulk.

A derivation of the transfer velocity from the concentration profiles is given by (Coantic 1986). The calculations will be omitted here but the dependency of the transfer velocity is consistent with most experimental values. Especially the Schmidt number dependency is consistent with the experiments within the margins of error. For sufficiently high Schmidt numbers ($Sc > 100$) the following proportionality for k holds:

$$k \propto Sc^{(-1 + \frac{1}{m})} u_* \quad (2.42)$$

The value m in the exponent of eq. 2.42 can be 2 or 3 depending on the boundary conditions (see eq. 2.35). This yields Schmidt number exponents, $n = 1 - (1/m)$, of $2/3$ for the rigid wall case

and $1/2$ for the free interface. For heat ($Sc \approx 6$) (Deacon 1977) found a dependency to a Schmidt number exponent of 0.61 caused by the influence of higher order terms which come into play for a thicker boundary layer, i.e. lower Schmidt numbers.

2.1.3 Surface renewal models

The surface renewal model assumes that transport through the aqueous boundary layer is caused by diffusion. In addition to diffusion, mass is transported means of an exchange of small volumes between the boundary layer and the water bulk. This is caused by eddies that penetrate into the boundary layer in statistical time intervals and transport water from the surface into the well mixed bulk. An illustration of this assumed process is found in (Asher and Pankow 1991) (fig. 2.6). The first attempt for modeling such renewal processes was made by postulating periodical renewal events (Higbie 1935). Later this exchange process was explained by statistical or random renewal events ((Danckwerts 1951) and (Harriott 1962)).

Figure 2.6: *Highly simplified schematic diagram of surface renewal processes (from (Asher and Pankow 1991))*

The renewal process can also be explained using an addition to the film model which is shown schematically in fig. 2.7. The liquid is divided into two regions as is already familiar from the film model but an additional exchange process from any point in the boundary region into the bulk is added. This renewal process brings fluid with the bulk concentration c_{bulk} into the boundary layer and to the surface and fluid from the surface back into the bulk.

The mathematical description of such an exchange process is a certain statistical renewal rate λ for boundary layer fluid elements. Adding of chemical reactions to the transfer process can be easily done by simply adding an additional rate constant λ_{chem} .

Figure 2.7: *The surface renewal theory for mass transfer. The liquid is pictured as two regions, a large well-mixed bulk and a surface region that is renewed so fast that it behaves as a thick film. The surface renewal is caused by larger eddies or liquid flow from the bulk. (from (Cussler 1984))*

Usually λ is written as a power of the depth z (Jähne 1985)

$$\lambda = \gamma_p z^p, \quad \text{with } p \geq 0. \quad (2.43)$$

where the case for $p = 0$ describes the classical surface renewal model that was first used by (Higbie 1935) and (Danckwerts 1951) where the renewal rate is not depth dependent. Especially the classical hydrodynamic assumption that a particle at the surface has to stay at the surface is violated. For $p > 0$ the renewal rate becomes zero at the water surface fulfilling the convergence criterion for surface films. The turbulent transport term in eq. 2.5 becomes:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \langle c'w' \rangle = -\gamma_p z^p \bar{c}, \quad (2.44)$$

where for simplicity the concentration of the gases is assumed to be zero in the bulk. Therefore the equation

$$\frac{\partial \bar{c}}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 \bar{c}}{\partial z^2} - \gamma_p z^p \bar{c} \quad (2.45)$$

remains to be solved. Using the above dimensionless scaling parameters (cf. eq. 2.34) the equation can be reduced to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \bar{c}_+}{\partial t_+} &= \frac{\partial^2 \bar{c}_+}{\partial z_+^2} - \gamma_{p+} \bar{c}_+, \\ \text{with } \gamma_{p+} &= \gamma_p z_*^p. \end{aligned} \quad (2.46)$$

The boundary conditions for solving them in the steady state are

$$j_+ = \begin{cases} \frac{\partial \bar{c}_+}{\partial z_+} \Big|_{z_+=0} & = 1 \\ \lim_{z_+ \rightarrow \infty} & = 0. \end{cases} \quad (2.47)$$

Only the solution for $p = 0$ has an analytical solution with an exponential concentration profile:

$$\bar{c}_+(z_+) = \exp(-z_+) \quad (2.48)$$

For $p = 1$ the equation is a so called Airy differential equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \bar{c}_+}{\partial z_+^2} = \gamma_{p+} z_+ \bar{c}_+, \quad (2.49)$$

which has the Airy function as a solution for the concentration profile:

$$\bar{c}_+(z_+) = \frac{1}{\text{Ai}(0)} \text{Ai} \left(\frac{\text{Ai}(0)}{\text{Ai}'(0)} z_+ \right). \quad (2.50)$$

The primed letters stand for the derivative with respect to z . $\text{Ai}(0)$ and $\text{Ai}(0)/\text{Ai}'(0)$ have the approximate values of 0.3550 and 1.372, respectively. Figure 2.5 shows both cases in a dimensionless plot (black curves).

Similar to the small eddy model the surface renewal model can predict the right Schmidt number dependency of the transfer velocity (*Csanady* 1990). Omitting the derivation the result is:

$$k \propto \text{Sc}^{(-1 + \frac{1}{p+2})} u_* \quad (2.51)$$

The Schmidt number exponent, $n = 1 - 1/(p+2)$, becomes 2/3 or 1/2 depending on the boundary conditions. For a free surface this is consistent with early results by (*Higbie* 1935) using periodic renewal events:

$$k = 1.13(D \cdot \lambda)^{1/2} \quad (2.52)$$

Conclusions from the previously described models

Measuring transfer velocities the surface renewal model as well as the small eddy model both predict the same Schmidt number exponent dependency. Even elaborate multi-tracer mass balance experiments can only measure the dependency on external parameters, like u_* , and the Schmidt number exponent. This dependency shows when the transition from a solid wall to a mobile interface regime takes place. However it cannot give any insight into the mechanisms controlling air-water mass transfer. This leads to the conclusion that no experimental techniques that inherently integrate over the complete water surface are able to distinguish between gas exchange models. In contrast to their prediction of transfer velocities the two models do differ significantly in their mean concentration profiles. The larger scale turbulence postulated by the surface renewal model gives way to a faster decrease of the mean concentration into the bulk. Therefore experimental techniques allowing for concentration measurements within the aqueous mass boundary layer do offer a possibility for distinguishing the two models.

2.1.4 Models based on Monte Carlo simulations

A different approach to model mass transfer across the aqueous boundary layer is to relate transfer to the fluctuating velocity field. This procedure does not have to make the same simplifications that went into the previously explained models. For example the usual approach to expand the concentration into a Taylor series (eq. 2.16) assumes that the velocity fluctuations are small compared to the mean values, which is not proven.

The concentration field can be related to the time-and-space-varying velocity field through the mass balance equation (eq. 2.5), where all quantities are made dimensionless using the friction velocity, u_* , the kinematic viscosity, ν , and the bulk concentration, c_{bulk} (*Campbell and Hanratty 1982*):

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial c}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial c}{\partial z} = \frac{1}{Sc} \left(\frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial z^2} \right). \quad (2.53)$$

The dimensionless time averaged concentration is described by the boundary-layer approximation:

$$0 = \frac{1}{Sc} \frac{d^2 \bar{c}}{dz^2} - \frac{d\langle c'w' \rangle}{dz}, \quad (2.54)$$

where $\langle c'w' \rangle$ is the dimensionless Reynold's transport term (cf. 2.5). Variations of the mass transfer coefficient with time are calculated by solving the mass balance equation using random velocity input, i.e. Monte Carlo simulations. The linearized version of eq. 2.53 for a solid boundary neglecting terms nonlinear in the fluctuating quantities was explored by (*Campbell and Hanratty 1982*). For large Schmidt numbers this **linear theory** leads to:

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + \beta z^2 \frac{d\bar{c}}{dz} = \frac{1}{Sc} \frac{\partial^2 c'}{\partial z^2} \quad (2.55)$$

For high Schmidt numbers the Reynolds transport is controlled by fluctuations of much lower frequency than the most energetic velocity fluctuations (*Campbell and Hanratty 1982*). This means that the molecular diffusion layer close to a **solid wall** acts as low pass filter. Only low frequency velocity fluctuations are effective in transporting mass and in causing velocity fluctuations. The results are given in terms of the input velocity spectral density function, $W_\beta(\omega)$, and the power spectrum of the fluctuating dimensionless mass transfer coefficient, $W_k(\omega)$. A comparison of the spectral function of $W_k(\omega)$, measured by (*Shaw 1976*), and the spectral function of the transverse component of the velocity gradient at the wall, W_γ , is given in the left hand plot of fig. 2.8. The right hand plot of fig. 2.8 gives the calculated spectral function of the Reynolds transport, $\langle c'w' \rangle$ at $Sc=1000$. Comparing these two plots shows that turbulent transport of mass is not controlled by the most energetic velocity fluctuations.

Figure 2.8: *Left: Experimental spectra compared with results from linear theory for a solid boundary. Right: Spectrum of Reynolds transport calculated from linear theory. Comparing the two plots shows that turbulent transport of mass is not controlled by the most energetic velocity fluctuations (both plots from (Campbell and Hanratty 1982)).*

The **nonlinear form** of the mass balance equations was evaluated by the same authors (*Campbell and Hanratty 1983*). The results confirm the picture of turbulent mass transfer at a solid boundary presented by the solution of the linear mass balance equations. Again there is no difference between mass transfer rates calculated from a velocity input containing a spectrum of all frequencies and those calculated from a velocity input containing only low frequencies (fig. 2.9). The upper part of the plot shows three input signals, β , with three different cut-off frequencies, n_{co} . The lower three plots show the resulting transfer velocities, k , for each of the above input signals. Even if the velocity signal is filtered so that 95% of the energy has been removed ($n_{co} = 0.0041$), changes in the calculated $k(t)$ values can be detected but the overall shape of the relation remains the same.

For the calculated influence of Sc on the transfer velocity, k , it is found that $k \sim Sc^{-0.70}$. Thus for the predictions of the Schmidt number exponent (*Campbell and Hanratty 1983*) differ slightly from the predictions by the small eddy and the surface renewal model. Those other models predict a Schmidt number exponent of $-2/3$. Experimental values usually obtained with dual tracer experiments are not precise enough to distinguish between the $-2/3$ or -0.7 dependency.

For a **mobile interface** computer simulations were performed by (*McCready et al. 1986*) and (*Back and McCready 1988*). They found that mass transfer at a mobile boundary is fundamentally different from the one at a solid boundary. Velocity fluctuations of all frequencies are playing a significant role. Spectra at a mobile as well as a solid boundary are shown in fig. 2.10. At the mobile interface the median frequency for mass transfer is the same as for the velocity spectrum.

Figure 2.9: *The time variation of the mass transfer coefficient obtained with the input velocity low pass filtered at different values (nonlinear model for a solid boundary). Top three signals: input signals, β , filtered with three different cut-off frequencies, n_{co} . Lower three plots: resulting transfer velocities, k , for each of the above input signals. (from (Campbell and Hanratty 1983)).*

No damping is occurring for this case (McCready *et al.* 1986). The Schmidt number exponent dependency of the transfer velocity, k , is $k \sim Sc^{-0.5}$. Thus it is the same as the one predicted by the other models for a mobile interface.

A transfer of the above results to wave spectra and ocean waves was carried out by (Back and McCready 1988). They conclude that since all wave lengths play a significant role a peak in the wave spectra around frequencies of 10 to 20 Hz (fig. 2.11) causes a predominant influence of these short waves on gas transfer. The interaction of the turbulent air flow causes extremely large variations in the interfacial stress which are relaxed by inducing flows within the liquid film which

Figure 2.10: Comparison of the frequency spectra of the mass transfer fluctuations at a mobile boundary and a solid boundary (from (McCready et al. 1986)).

originate at the interface and are extremely effective at transporting mass. This scheme implies a change of mass transfer rates with wave phase, i.e. boundary layer thickness should correlate with wave phase.

Figure 2.11: Comparison between the (a) wave amplitude spectrum and (b) normal velocity gradient spectrum calculated for the shear stress variation mechanism. All variables are dimensionless (from (Back and McCready 1988)).

Chapter 3

Measurements of Concentration Profiles

The aim of this chapter is to introduce the two methods known to be capable of measuring non-intrusively concentration profiles in the aqueous mass boundary layer. Both are laser-induced fluorescence (LIF) techniques, which were developed independently and first introduced at the 2nd International Symposium on Gas Transfer at Water Surfaces at Minneapolis, Minnesota in 1991. The two techniques have the fact in common that the fluorescence of a dye dissolved in water is excited by a laser light sheet and the fluorescent light is imaged by a CCD camera. In spite of this the physical and chemical processes that make the concentration profiles visible are different.

- The technique that will be described here first was developed at the University of Heidelberg and uses the fluorescent dye *fluorescein* (Jähne 1991). *Fluorescein* dissolves into a singly and a doubly protonated anion of which only the latter is highly fluorescent. The ratio of the two species is dependent on the local pH value and therefore *fluorescein* qualifies as an indicator for acidity. Thus an intentional chemical reaction at the water surface generates a visible concentration gradient which then can be studied.
- The second technique was developed at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign and measures the concentration of dissolved oxygen in the water (Wolff *et al.* 1991). Oxygen offers a non-radiative relaxation path for the excited molecules of the dye pyrene butyric acid (*PBA*). This process is called quenching. The loss of fluorescence light is a function of the dissolved oxygen concentration.

In this chapter only the principles necessary for measuring concentration profiles are introduced. Appendix A provides a more detailed insight into the processes of absorption, fluorescence and fluorescence quenching.

3.1 The fluorescein method

The *fluorescein* technique measures the concentration of the doubly charged, i.e. unprotonated *fluorescein* anions. This section is divided into two subsections. Firstly the underlying processes of this technique are described. Then an estimate of the necessary and measurable concentration changes for the *fluorescein* technique is given. The following subsection works out a prove that the measured fluorescence signal is a linear function of the concentration of the doubly charged anion. For this it is necessary to have a closer look at the absorption and fluorescence characteristics of *fluorescein*.

3.1.1 Principle of the technique

Figure 3.1: Schematic representation of the processes taking place in visualizing the vertical concentration profiles with the fluorescein method. First HCl is absorbed at the water surface with a fluorescein solution with equal concentrations of the fluorescent and non-fluorescent anion species. This causes a concentration gradient between the water surface and the bulk resulting in a concentration profile across the aqueous boundary layer.

The starting point for the measurements is a solution of *fluorescein* in water with equal concentrations of the highly fluorescent doubly charged anion and the less fluorescent singly charged anion. The way to prepare a solution with such properties will be described in the next subsection (3.1.2). The fluorescence is excited by a laser beam penetrating through the water surface. Neglecting absorption effects at this point a uniform fluorescence light intensity over the laser beam should be visible. Now small amounts of HCl gas are injected into the air space. If the air space can be assumed well mixed the HCl will hit the water surface and dissociate. At the water surface the HCl dissociates instantaneously and protonates the doubly charged anions. This leads to a shift in concentrations of the *fluorescein* anion species at the water surface (see fig. 3.1). The HCl gas that initiated the process completely dissociates at the water surface and the remaining Cl^- ions start diffusing into the bulk. In the bulk the concentrations are still the same, i.e. equal concentrations of doubly and singly charged *fluorescein* anions. Therefore a concentration difference of anion species

exists across the boundary layer. This leads to the development of a concentration profile across the aqueous boundary layer. Looking at the fluorescence light intensity along the laser beam a concentration profile can now be seen. This profile is caused by an increase of the concentration of the highly fluorescent doubly charged anion from the diminished surface concentration to the original concentration in the bulk. This concentration profile is the analogue to a concentration profile of any inert gas. The difference is that it is highly visible and that the Schmidt number that has to be considered is the one of *fluorescein* ($Sc \approx 2440$) which is higher than the one for most gases. The relevant Schmidt number for the transfer can be different because the diffusion of the fluorescein anions is electro-chemically coupled with the faster diffusion of the Cl^- ions.

3.1.2 Necessary and measurable concentration changes

This subsection will show why the above described processes are a valid replacement for an inert gas and what concentration changes are necessary to get a measurable concentration gradient. At this point the definitions of the pH and p*K* value shall be briefly reviewed. pH is defined as the negative common logarithm of the H^+ concentration: $pH = -\log [H^+]$. The p*K* value is also called the acidity constant and is a measure for the acidity of a certain solution. It is the negative common logarithm of the so called equilibrium constant *K*. For a solution of *fluorescein* in water the chemical equilibrium in water is described by the equilibrium constant:

$$\frac{[H^+][R^{2-}]}{[HR^-]} = K \quad (3.1)$$

Therefore the p*K* value for the protonation of the doubly charged *fluorescein* anion $[R^{2-}]$ is given by:

$$pK = -\log \frac{[H^+][R^{2-}]}{[HR^-]} \quad (3.2)$$

In all of the following experiments the fluorescent indicator *fluorescein* is used at its buffer point in a dilute solution (a concentration of 2×10^{-5} M was used here). The buffer point of a solution is defined by equal concentrations of the two ionic forms HR^- and R^{2-} . The buffer point, i.e. the point with equal concentrations of the protonated and unprotonated anions is obviously reached if $pH = pK$. The p*K* value for fluorescein is $pK = 6.5$ (*Guyot et al.* 1975). At a pH value close to the buffer point of fluorescein the concentrations of OH^- and H^+ (or better H_3O^+) ions are much lower than the concentrations of HR^- and R^{2-} . Since $[OH^-] \times [H_3O^+] = 10^{-14}$ the concentrations are:

$$[OH^-] = 10^{-7.5} \text{ M}, \quad [H_3O^+] = 10^{-6.5} \text{ M} \quad \text{and} \quad [HR^-] = [R^{2-}] = 10^{-5} \text{ M}.$$

That is to say that we have an excess of dye ions by at least 1.5 orders of magnitude in the bulk.

Now HCl is injected into the air space. The gas is transported to the air/water interface, where it dissociates instantaneously. The rate constant for the dissociation of HCl to H^+ and Cl^- is

$k = 2.7 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ (Graedel and Mandich 1986). There it protonates the *fluorescein*'s doubly charged anions at the water surface generating an excess number of the low fluorescent singly charged anions HR^- . The rate constant for this protonation is given by (Yam *et al.* 1988) with $k = 2.5 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. Calculations using these values and assuming pure diffusional transport show that more than 99% of the possible *fluorescein* reactions take place within $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ from the water surface. Since the HCl concentration is zero at the interface, the HCl flux density into the water according to eq. 2.3 is given by

$$j_a = k_a \times [\text{HCl}] \quad (3.3)$$

where k_a is the air sided transfer velocity and $[\text{HCl}]$ the bulk concentration of HCl in the air space. As we already saw the generated H_3O^+ ions react with the R^{2-} ions to form HR^- . This process constitutes a sink for R^{2-} and a source for HR^- , resulting in flux densities equal to the flux of HCl (due to conservation of mass). Therefore

$$j_w = k_w \times \Delta[\text{HR}^-] = -k_w \times \Delta[\text{R}^{2-}] \quad (3.4)$$

The H_3O^+ concentration adjusts in such a way that eq. 3.1 is maintained everywhere, but since HR^- and R^{2-} are significantly more abundant than H_3O^+ no significant concentration changes for HR^- and R^{2-} occur due to this chemical reaction on their way through the boundary layer.

The HCl gas concentration which is necessary to cause a significant change in the liquid can be estimated as follows. Since the fluxes on the air and water side have to be equal, we can use eqs. (3.3) and (3.4) to determine $[\text{HCl}]$ as a function of $\Delta[\text{R}^{2-}]$.

$$[\text{HCl}] = k_w/k_a \times \Delta[\text{R}^{2-}] \quad (3.5)$$

The quotient k_w/k_a is typically in the order of 1/500 (cf. (Jähne 1985)). Assuming that we can detect a 1% change in fluorescence yields

$$\frac{\Delta[\text{R}^{2-}]}{I} = \frac{k_a}{k_w} \times \frac{[\text{HCl}]}{I} = 10^{-2}, \quad (3.6)$$

where $I = [\text{R}^{2-} + \text{HR}^-]$ is the total *fluorescein* concentration which is $2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$. With the approximations made above we get a value for $[\text{HCl}] / I$ of 5×10^{-5} . This results in a minimum HCl gas concentration of $[\text{HCl}]_{\min} = 10^{-9} \text{ mole/l}$, which is approximately 20 ppb. This enormous sensitivity is caused by the low aqueous ion concentrations (10^{-5} M) as well as the air-sided controlled transfer process of the HCl ($k_w/k_a \approx 1/500$). As an effect of this it is absolutely crucial to use deionized water. Regular drinking water has ion concentrations in the order of at least 10^{-3} M .

In principle the gas HCl can be replaced by any other acidic or basic gas but certain effects have to be considered. When replacing the HCl gas with CO_2 the transfer process becomes water side controlled and therefore the fluxes are smaller by 3 orders of magnitude. In addition to that, CO_2 produces only 1% of the ion fluxes of a highly reactive gas. This results in a necessary CO_2 concentration that is 10^5 times higher than the one for HCl. This means that for using CO_2 with the *fluorescein* method CO_2 concentrations in the percent range would be necessary (Jähne 1992).

3.1.3 The pH dependence of fluorescein fluorescence

To understand the behavior of the system chosen to investigate the mechanisms of mass transfer it is necessary to have a closer look at the behavior of *fluorescein* with changing pH value. It is crucial that the fluorescence intensity is a function solely of the concentration of the transported component. In this case the *fluorescein* intensity has to be a function of one of the anion species.

Fluorescein is known to have four ionic forms in aqueous solutions: doubly charged anion, singly charged anion, neutral molecule and cation. In the pH range of interest here (from pH 5.8 to pH 8) only the doubly and singly charged anions and the neutral molecule are present. Figure 3.2 shows the three ionic forms in the chinoid representation.

Figure 3.2: a) neutral molecule, b) anion, c) doubly charged anion (Only one of the respective resonance structures is shown).

The deprotonation of the carboxylic acid group and the alcohol group brings forward changes in the absorption spectrum as well as in the quantum yield and the fluorescence spectrum. To show the dependency of fluorescence on the concentration of the doubly charged anion a profound consideration of the behavior of the *fluorescein* molecules is necessary.

In order to get a quantitative information of *fluorescein* fluorescence one has to be able to re-calculate the measured fluorescence intensity to the concentration of a single ionic form. Knowing the protonation constants (see the subsection on pK values further down in this chapter for the values.) a formula for re-calculation can be found. The equilibrium constants are defined as:

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{H}_2\text{R}]}{[\text{H}_3\text{R}^+]}, \quad (3.7)$$

$$K_2 = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{HR}^-]}{[\text{H}_2\text{R}]}, \quad (3.8)$$

$$K_3 = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{R}^{2-}]}{[\text{HR}^-]}. \quad (3.9)$$

Using the equations 3.8 and 3.9 one gets

$$\frac{K_3 [\text{H}_2\text{R}]}{[\text{H}^+]} = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{R}^{2-}]}{K_2},$$

which leads to an equation for the doubly charged anion concentration:

$$[\text{R}^{2-}] = K_2 K_3 \frac{[\text{H}_2\text{R}]}{[\text{H}^+]^2}. \quad (3.10)$$

In this equation we can substitute the H^+ concentration by the pH value ($\text{H}^+ = 10^{-\text{pH}}$):

$$[\text{R}^{2-}] = K_2 K_3 [\text{H}_2\text{R}] 10^{2\text{pH}} \quad (3.11)$$

Neglecting the *fluorescein* cation (which is allowable for the pH range of interest here) we can replace the concentration of the free acid $[\text{H}_2\text{R}]$ by the total concentration of *fluorescein* c :

$$[\text{H}_2\text{R}] = c - [\text{R}^{2-}] - [\text{HR}^-].$$

If we substitute this in equation 3.11 we get a relation between the concentration of the doubly charged anion and the pH value:

$$[\text{R}^{2-}] = \frac{K_2 K_3 10^{2\text{pH}} c}{1 + K_2 K_3 10^{2\text{pH}} + K_2 10^{\text{pH}}}. \quad (3.12)$$

Substituting the doubly charged anion concentration with the relation in eq. 3.11 we get an analogue equation for the singly charged anion:

$$[\text{HR}^-] = \frac{K_2 10^{\text{pH}} c}{1 + K_2 K_3 10^{2\text{pH}} + K_2 10^{\text{pH}}}. \quad (3.13)$$

Acidity constants of fluorescein

In the literature different values for the acidity constants for fluorescein can be found. The following table gives an overview over these values.

$\text{p}K_1$ ($\text{H}_3\text{R}^+ \leftrightarrow \text{H}_2\text{R}$)	$\text{p}K_2$ ($\text{H}_2\text{R} \leftrightarrow \text{HR}^-$)	$\text{p}K_3$ ($\text{HR}^- \leftrightarrow \text{R}^{2-}$)	author
1.95	5.05	7.0	(Zanker and Peter 1958)
2.2	4.4	6.7	(Lindqvist 1960)
2.2	4.4	6.5	(Guyot et al. 1975)
		6.7	(Fompeydie et al. 1979)
2.27	4.32	6.5	(Mchedlov-Petrosyan 1979)
2.3	4.6	7.0	(Privalova and Fofonova 1982)

To the author the work by (Guyot *et al.* 1975) seems to be the most profound and careful analysis. In this work all aspects of fluorescein chemistry like kinetic and secondary effects were carefully considered. Therefore for any further applications these values were adopted: $pK_1 = 2.2$, $pK_2 = 4.4$ and $pK_3 = 6.5$.

If the protolytic equilibrium is established during the lifetime of the excited singlet state, it shows a different equilibrium constant (see Appendix A),

$$K^* = \frac{[R^{2-*}]}{[RH^{-*}]} 10^{pH} \quad .$$

Looking at the fluorescence of a dye one has to consider a superposition of both constants: K for the absorption and K^* for the emission. In the literature highly differing pK^* values are given. These values of the excited singlet state usually do not come from experimental values but are calculated using the so called Förster cycle (Förster 1950):

$$pK = pK^* + 2.1 \cdot 10^{-3} \Delta\nu_{cm^{-1}} \quad .$$

where $\Delta\nu_{cm^{-1}}$ is the frequency difference between the last two absorption maxima (expressed in cm^{-1}) of the acid to the one of the basic form. For applying the Förster cycle kinetic considerations have to be taken into account since it assumes that the protolytic equilibrium is completely established during the lifetime of the excited state. The experimental data as well as kinetic considerations do not satisfy the above condition for the Förster cycle for *fluorescein*. (Guyot *et al.* 1975) proved that at a pH of 6.3 the concentrations of the ionic forms R^{*2-} versus HR^{*-} in the first excited state are the same as the ionic forms R^{2-} versus HR^{-} in the ground state. This means that the protolytic equilibrium is not established and for all practical considerations the difference between pK and pK^* can be neglected.

The pH dependent absorption of fluorescein

As mentioned above *fluorescein* shows a significant change in the absorption coefficient with pH. From pH 3 to pH 9 the absorption coefficient at a wavelength of 488 nm changes by a factor of 20. The following figure (3.3) shows a plot of the absorption coefficient ϵ at $\lambda = 488$ nm vs. pH. This is the output wavelength of the argon ion laser used in the experiments and the maximum of the absorption spectrum. Therefore no other wavelengths will be considered here.

Quantum yield of fluorescein

The fluorescence quantum yield Φ of a dye molecule is defined as the ratio of absorbed photons to emitted photons. Both quantities have to be measured over the complete spectrum. Various

¹These data points are not corrected for re-absorption/re-emission. Three typical sets of error bars are drawn along the curve. The errors are caused by the uncertainty in concentration measurements ($< 5\%$) and in length measurement (< 0.03 mm).

Figure 3.3: Change of the absorption coefficient ϵ ($\lambda = 488 \text{ nm}$) with pH value. The plot includes values by several authors and own measurements¹ which are shown as a line through all the values. This experiment is described in more detail in the appendix or in (Münsterer 1993). The black solid line is an interpolation through the data points by (Martin and Lindqvist 1975) using the pK_a values by (Guyot et al. 1975).

methods have been proposed for measuring Φ , based primarily on comparison of solutions under investigation with references whose quantum yield is known (Krasovitskii and Bolotin 1988). The quantum yield of the different ionic forms of *fluorescein* was determined by different authors. The quantum yield for the doubly charged anion can be measured directly. The quantum yield of the neutral molecule and the anion can only be deduced using the independently measured pK values. The quantum yield for the *fluorescein* doubly charged anion is given by several authors ((Weber and Teale 1958), (Guyot et al. 1975), and (Arbeloa 1980)) as $\Phi_{f_{R^{2-}}} = 0.92$. For the anion the only reliable value seems to be the one by (Guyot et al. 1975) with $\Phi_{f_{HR^-}} = 0.26$. (Martin and Lindqvist 1975) are more cautious considering the uncertainties in the pK values and give a range from 0.25 to 0.35 for $\Phi_{f_{HR^-}}$. (Guyot et al. 1975) also give the neutral molecule quantum yield as $\Phi_{f_{H_2R}} = 0.14$. The following plot illustrates the change of quantum yield with pH value with data by (Razwadowski 1961) who gives values for the complete range of changing pH.

Figure 3.4: Quantum yield Φ versus pH value by (Rozwadowski 1961)

The pH dependent fluorescence of fluorescein

The upper part of figure 3.5 shows the fluorescence spectra of *fluorescein* for different pH values. The shape as well as the amplitude, i.e. the quantum yield of the spectra change with pH. In spite of this the CCD camera will not be able to detect the integral over these spectra. One reason for this is that the CCD's sensitivity is not uniform over the spectral range. The other reason is the re-absorption of fluorescence light by the solution. This effect is caused by an overlap of the absorption and emission spectra. For this setup where the pH change takes place only locally in the aqueous mass boundary layer a constant pH value for the re-absorbing solution body can be assumed. The lower part of figure 3.5 shows the effect of re-absorption on the spectra. All the fluorescence light below 500 nm is annihilated and re-absorption completely changes the shape of the spectra below 530 nm.

Linearity of fluorescence intensity

For an ideal system fluorescence intensity should be proportional to the concentration of the doubly charged anion. This can be seen by assuming absorbed intensity as well as fluorescence intensity (\mathcal{I}_{abs} and $\mathcal{I}_{emission}$) as a function of singly and doubly charged anion concentration:

$$\mathcal{I}_{abs} = \chi_{single}[\text{HR}^-] + \chi_{double}[\text{R}^{2-}],$$

where χ is the molar absorbance for the respective anions.

$$\mathcal{I}_{emission} = \Phi_{single}[\text{HR}^-] + \Phi_{double}[\text{R}^{2-}],$$

Figure 3.5: *Top part: Fluorescence spectra of fluorescein for different pH values. The spectra were scaled using quantum yields by (Razwadowski 1961). (1): (Martin and Lindqvist 1975), (2): (Razwadowski 1961). Bottom part: Fluorescence spectra taking into account re-absorption by a 5 cm, 2×10^{-5} M solution body at pH 7. These spectra are calculated from the spectra in the top part using absorption values by (Martin and Lindqvist 1975).*

Φ_{single} and Φ_{double} are the molar quantum yields of the singly and doubly charged anions. This assumes of course that there is no interference between the two forms of fluorescence. Total fluorescence intensity is the product of the absorbed and the emitted intensities ($\mathcal{I}_{abs} \times \mathcal{I}_{emission}$) which for this highly simplified case is a function of $[R^{2-}]$.

Nevertheless as mentioned above a change in pH changes the absorption and fluorescence spectra, the quantum yield and the fluorescence spectra are altered by re-absorption. Therefore it is no longer possible to rely on a linear behavior of fluorescence intensity \mathcal{I} versus concentration of the doubly charged anion $[R^{2-}]$. Using the pH dependent absorbance from 3.1.3 and the fluorescence spectra after re-absorption from 3.1.3 the dependency of \mathcal{I} versus $[R^{2-}]$ can be calculated. $[R^{2-}]$

can be calculated from the pH value using eq. 3.12. Figure 3.6 shows this relation. The upright triangles show the dependency with re-absorption. The inverted triangles show the same dependency introducing into the calculations the spectral response of the CCD and of a dichroic mirror in the optical path. The stars show the scaled result of an experiment trying to separate fluorescence pH value and reabsorption pH value to reproduce the calculated results. The experimental setup for this experiment is explained in appendix B. The plot clearly shows that for a pH value below 8 the deviation from linearity is less than 4%.

Figure 3.6: *Intensity of the fluorescein fluorescence versus concentration of the doubly charged fluorescein anion. The curves are calculated from literature values for the absorbance at 488 nm (Martin and Lindqvist 1975), fluorescence spectra (Martin and Lindqvist 1975) and (Razwadowski 1961) and quantum yields (Razwadowski 1961). The circles show the calculated response for an ideal system without re-absorption and an ideal CCD response. The upright triangles describe the system with re-absorption in a solution body as it is used in the experiments. The inverted triangles show the response taking into account re-absorption, the spectral response of the CCD. (The spectral response values were taken from the data sheets of the CCD manufacturer Dalsa Corp., Waterloo, Ontario, Canada.). The stars show the experimental results of the measurement of fluorescence vs. pH value with reabsorption by a solution body at a constant pH value.*

Concluding the characteristics of fluorescein

Concluding the above sections *fluorescein* is a tracer capable of visualizing the transfer processes through the aqueous mass boundary layer for the following reasons:

- The *fluorescein* method needs only minute amounts of a starter gas (preferably HCl) to start an indicator reaction that develops a concentration profile over the aqueous mass boundary layer.
- Fluorescein displays an absorption maximum at $\lambda = 488 \text{ nm}$ ($\epsilon = 7 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at pH 7).
- Fluorescein has a quantum yield in the range between 0.26 (at pH 3) and 0.92 (at pH > 8).
- Fluorescence intensity is a linear function of the concentration of one of the transported ion species.
- The di-sodium salt of *fluorescein* (uranine) is highly soluble in water (solubility 40 mg/ml) (*Green* 1990).
- Fluorescein solutions do not display surface active films in dilute solutions. The static surface tension for a $1.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ solution is within the margins of error the same as for distilled water (*Billen* 1985).

3.2 The oxygen quenching method

Figure 3.7: Fluorescence quenching of PBA fluorescence by the presence of dissolved oxygen (data from own experiments, $K = (683 \pm 70) \text{ l/mole}$ at $T = 298 \text{ K}$, within the margins of error of the K value first published by (Vaughan and Weber 1970); $K = (645 \pm 79) \text{ l/mole}$).

One problem in measuring fluorescence quantitatively is the fact that fluorescence is quenched or disturbed by the presence of other molecules in the solution. These molecules offer a path for the excited molecule to relax back into the ground state without the emission of a photon. (Appendix A explains the physical background of this effect.) This effect was first used by (Vaughan and Weber 1970) to measure the concentration of the quencher oxygen in living cell tissue. (Wolff *et al.* 1991) adapted this technique for measuring concentration profiles of oxygen in the aqueous mass boundary layer. In this case, the concentration of the dye is kept constant in the water, but the concentration of the quenching molecule (oxygen) varies over the aqueous mass boundary layer. The presence of oxygen in the water causes the molecules to relax to their ground state through non-radiative collisions. The decrease in fluorescence intensity is quantitatively described by the Stern-Volmer equation:

$$I(c) = \frac{I_0}{1 + Kc}, \quad (3.14)$$

where I_0 is the fluorescence intensity with no quencher present, K is the quenching constant and c is the concentration of the quencher. The best fluorescent dye for this kind of experiments, described by (Vaughan and Weber 1970), (Wolff *et al.* 1991) and (Wolff and Hanratty 1994) is pyrene butyric acid (PBA). It shows an approximate 15% loss of fluorescence intensity with

dissolved oxygen concentrations increasing from 0.8 to 8 mg/l (see fig. 3.7) as is the case for the degased Heidelberg flume.

The advantages of the oxygen quenching technique are the following:

- The surface concentration is a well-defined property of the system under investigation. The surface concentration should always equalize the equilibrium concentration of the oxygen partial pressure in the air space.
- No chemical reactions are involved in this visualization technique. The quenching process is caused by molecule collisions and directly measures the concentration of the well known tracer oxygen.
- The absorbance of the *PBA* solution is independent of external parameters like pH value.
- *PBA* does not show any absorption in the spectral range of visual light. This makes a possible combination with other imaging techniques easier.

On the other hand the oxygen quenching technique also has several, mostly technical, disadvantages.

- *PBA* has its absorption peak in the UV region at 345 nm. Lasers emitting in this region are mostly pulsed (frequency doubled ruby lasers or N₂ lasers). This makes the acquisition of continuous time series, i.e. of image sequences technically difficult.
- *PBA* fluorescence ranges from 370 to 430 nm with peaks at 375 and 400 nm. Although standard CCD sensors generally show lower responses for these wavelengths there are special CCD sensors available that have significant quantum yields in this spectral region. An example of the spectral response of such a CCD sensor is shown in fig. 3.8
- Simple observation shows that *PBA* fluorescence, i.e. the quantum yield of *PBA*, is low. This combined with the above mentioned fluorescence wavelengths make it hard to measure *PBA* fluorescence with standard CCD cameras. The signal-to-noise ration is usually very poor.

An interesting application of the oxygen quenching of fluorescence is found in a totally different area of research. (Engler *et al.* 1992) describe a method of measuring the pressure distributions over an airplane wing. The pressure distribution is equivalent to the distribution of the oxygen partial pressure in the air. For this method some more aspects of fluorescence quenching like the temperature dependence (cf. (Münsterer 1993)) or the angle dependent emission of solid surfaces have to be considered.

Figure 3.8: Spectral response of different CCD sensors (from (SITE 1996)). The plot for the front illuminated cooled CCD shows a zero quantum efficiency below 400 nm.

3.3 Compatibility of the two techniques

Experiments show that the two dyes *fluorescein* and *PBA* exhibit a high degree of chemical and optical compatibility. Fluorescein fluorescence is neither affected by the presence of *PBA* in the solution nor significantly stimulated by the N_2 laser. The quenching of *fluorescein* fluorescence by oxygen can be neglected (much less than 1% over the concentration range investigated here (Chéchan 1946) and (Münsterer 1993)). The *PBA* fluorescence is not affected by the local pH value of the solution and is not stimulated by the argon ion laser. Fluorescein has only a very weak absorbance at the emission wavelength of the N_2 laser ($\lambda = 337$ nm). *PBA* is not stimulated by the argon ion laser at all. Fig. 3.9 shows the two absorption spectra.

PBA fluorescence is located between 340 and 420 nm whereas *fluorescein* fluorescence is located between 490 and 620 nm. This gives way to the possibility of separating the two fluorescence spectra with dichroic mirrors. The possibility of further interferences is discussed in detail in section 7.

Figure 3.9: Absorption spectra of pyrene butyric acid and fluorescein by (Vaughan and Weber 1970) and (Mota et al. 1991). At the emission wavelength of the N_2 laser (337 nm) fluorescein absorption is weak compared to the fluorescein absorption at 488 nm. PBA is not stimulated by the argon ion laser at 488 nm at all.

Chapter 4

Experimental Procedure

Experiments with the two laser induced fluorescence techniques described in the previous chapters were conducted in three different setups. For the experiments the author had access to two different facilities. One was a linear channel designed for the study of mass transfer in two phase flow at the Department of Chemical Engineering at the University of Illinois in Urbana-Champaign (UIUC), USA. The other one was the circular channel of the Institute for Environmental Physics at the University of Heidelberg (IUP). The experiments at the University of Illinois were conducted for different wind speeds at a wavy interface. The small water height of the channel at the UIUC allowed for simultaneous measurements of the *fluorescein* LIF technique with a wave slope measuring technique. The first experiment at the Heidelberg facility was a combination of the oxygen quenching with the *fluorescein* LIF technique with high wind shear and suppressed waves, i.e. a flat interface. The second set of experiments at the Heidelberg facility was carried out at wavy and smooth interfaces with simultaneous mean square slope measurements.

4.1 Setup at the University of Illinois

The channel at the Department of Chemical Engineering of the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign was built for studying mass transfer in two phase flows and flowing liquid films that are important in the field of chemical engineering. This channel has a length of 11 m and a cross section of 30.48 cm by 2.54 cm. The average water height is approximately 1 cm. These dimensions result in a fully developed wave field in the measuring section which is 4 m from the air inlet. The limited water height allows for measurements at a fully developed wavy surface without a sophisticated scanning mechanism to track the water surface. A sketch of this facility is shown in fig. 4.1.

The setup is shown in fig. 4.2. The fluorescence was excited with an 1.7 W Ar⁺ ion laser at a wavelength of 488 nm. A laser light sheet was produced by a scanning mirror with a frequency of 100 Hz. The scanning laser beam was focused at the water surface resulting in a sheet thickness of

Figure 4.1: Schematic of the two-phase flow channel at the Department of Chemical Engineering of the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign.

approximately $340\ \mu\text{m}$. This thickness was below the depth of field of the imaging system, which was $400\ \mu\text{m}$. The laser penetrated perpendicularly into the flume through a glass window at the bottom. This is only possible in this flume because absorption losses within the 1 cm water height are still acceptable. The fluorescence was imaged through a window at the channel side with an optical system using two achromatic lenses each having a focal length of 200 mm. Achromatic lenses are optimized for a setup where the image and the object each are in the focal plane of the subsequent lens. Therefore the light sheet and the CCD chip of the camera were in the focal planes of the respective lenses. To achieve a compact setup a mirror was mounted between the two lenses. The complete optical setup was tilted 9° to the horizontal. This was necessary to minimize shading of the measuring section by deeper wave troughs in the foreground. Nevertheless at a fully developed wave field some wave troughs did shade the measuring section statistically. A larger angle was not used because this would have resulted in even more severe optical distortions. For evaluating and understanding these distortions ray tracing calculations of the optical system were undertaken using the optical design program Zemax. Ray tracing is a numerical method of evaluating properties of an optical system by calculating the path of rays from the object through lenses and surfaces to the image plane. These calculations are done by applying geometrical considerations and Snell's law from one surface to the other. Fig. 4.3 shows the technical drawing of the optical setup leaving out the folding mirror which does not introduce significant optical distortions. A so called spot

Figure 4.2: *Experimental setup for the first set of experiments at the wind/wave facility of the Department of Chemical Engineering at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign. The complete optical setup is tilted approximately 9° to the horizontal to minimize shading of the measuring section by deeper wave troughs in the foreground.*

diagram of the optical system is shown in fig. 4.4. A spot diagram is formed by a plot of rays emitted at different angles and originating from a single point in the object plane. The intersection of each of these rays with the image plane is marked with a dot. Obviously for an ideal optical system these intersections should lie in a single point. A system of two achromatic lenses without an air-glass-water intersection comes fairly close to this ideal having diffraction limited resolution. The plot in fig. 4.4 shows that the tilted air glass water intersection introduces a significant amount of astigmatism. Therefore the system resolution is only in the order of $25\ \mu\text{m}$. Fig. 4.5 shows the line/edge response of the system which are the properties for imaging an ideal line and an ideal edge. The result of the edge response can also be measured easily by imaging a calibration target. The experimental result for the edge response is in good agreement with the calculated values.

Figure 4.3: *Technical drawing of the optical setup used at the channel of the UIUC. This setup was used as an input for ray tracing calculations of the optical system.*

The camera was a Dalsa CA-D1 camera with 256×256 pixels and a frame rate of up to 200 Hz. The frames were read out digitally via the digital camera interface of a Hyperspeed Technology XPi860 extension board. This board was equipped with 128 MByte of RAM memory allowing acquisition of 1800 frames or 9 s of images at 200 Hz. The camera was synchronized with the scanning laser beam. This setup minimized motion blur and resulted in a measured optical resolution of $16\ \mu\text{m}$.

A peristaltic pump was used to inject HCl gas at a constant rate into the air space of the flume. The injection point was approx. 1 m upstream of the optical measuring port.

The channel at the University of Illinois offers the possibility of combining the *fluorescein* technique with a technique measuring a two-dimensional wave slope field in time. As already mentioned before the water height of only 1 cm at this facility allows for the laser beam to penetrate into the water through a glass window at the bottom of the channel. Wave slopes were measured with the so called color imaging slope gauge. This technique is based on visualizing the one-dimensional wave slope with a refraction technique (Jähne 1989). The technique was improved by (Zhang and Cox 1994) to measure both slope components at the same time using color. For measuring two-dimensional slopes with higher resolution and with an intrinsic intensity correction the color imaging slope

Figure 4.4: *Spot diagram of the optical setup. If not explicitly expressed all length values are in μm . The tilted optical axis introduces an optical distortion called astigmatism. Spot diagrams for an image point on the optical axis and in the upper right hand corner of the image are shown. Astigmatism reduces the optical resolution to approx. $25\ \mu\text{m}$. The black circle denotes the diffraction limit.*

gauge (CISG) was further improved by (Balschbach *et al.* 1995). The CISG used here imaged a field of $25 \times 15\ \text{mm}$ at a rate of 60 Hz.

The laser beam penetrated the bottom of the flume at an angle of 34° against the vertical. This was necessary to avoid shading of the imaging slope gauge setup. The imaging slope gauge measured wave slopes in an area of 25 by $15\ \text{mm}$ at a rate of 60 Hz. The frame rate of the digital camera used for the concentration profile measurements was adjusted to 180 Hz. Both cameras and the laser beam were synchronized. For 6 conditions sequences of 8.3s were measured. The color imaging slope gauge is usually capable of measuring the long-wind and cross-wind slope component simultaneously. The CCD of the color camera of the CISG had to be protected against direct hits by the laser beam. For this a OG530 cutoff color filter was used. Therefore only two of the three color components could be measured at a time. Due to the changing background light of the *fluorescein* fluorescence the two colors had to be used in a setup where the second color is used for an intensity correction. Therefore the long-wind and cross-wind slopes were measured independently. The color camera of the CISG was shuttered so that the image acquisition was done while the laser beam was

Figure 4.5: *Line and edge response diagram for the optical system. This plot shows how an ideal line (at position 0 from 0.0 to 1.0) or an ideal edge (dashed lines in the plot) are imaged on the CCD. Digitization effects on the CCD are not considered here.*

outside of the camera's field of vision. Nevertheless this could not completely avoid over-exposure of the color images. The reason probably lies in the limited ability of the CCD's electronic shutter. The over-exposures caused a spiral distortion pattern in the images. Therefore an area of 640×25 pixels was selected from the frames. There was no over-exposures in this area and the position of the laser light sheet was right in the center of this section. The slope measurements were performed by Günther Balschbach. More details on the CISG measurements are presented in (*Balschbach 1997*).

Figure 4.6: (A color plate of this figure can be found as fig. 9.2 on page 116) *Experimental setup for the first set of experiments at the wind/wave facility of the Department of Chemical Engineering at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign. The pictures show a side view of the imaging optics and a frontal view with the imaging optics (left) and the laser light sheet (right).*

Figure 4.7: *Experimental setup for the combined experiments at the UIUC. The wave slope is visualized using an lighting system illuminating the water surface with a color wedge from below. Due to refraction each slope component is seen as the same color on the color wedge. The laser optics of the LIF technique is tilted 34° against the vertical to avoid shading by the CISG setup.*

Figure 4.8: Location of the laser light sheet in the imaging area of the CISG. A section of 640×25 pixels was selected from the wave slope images. There was no distortion by over-exposures in this area. The position of the laser light sheet is marked with a black line in the wave slope image.

4.2 Setup at the University of Heidelberg

The circular wind/wave facility at the Institute for Environmental Physics at the University of Heidelberg consists of a 30 cm wide and 70 cm high gas-tight annular channel with an outer diameter of 4 m. Wind is generated by a rotating paddle ring driven by 24 small DC motors. The channel is filled up to a height of 25 cm; so the water and air volumes are 0.88 and 1.6 m^3 , respectively. Fig. 4.9 shows a sketch of the channel.

Figure 4.9: *Schematic of the circular wind/wave facility at the University of Heidelberg. The outer diameter is 4 m, the channel width is 30 cm (from (Schmundt et al. 1995)).*

One of the major disadvantages of a circular flume is that the wind induced momentum input into the bulk causes a water current in the facility. The water body as a whole moves around the facility. This induces drift currents of up to 30 cm/s at the water surface. A linear moving bed facility in which the mean flow can be set to zero was first designed by (Tamburrino and Gulliver 1992). This idea has been adapted for the annular channel by inserting a moving bottom that can rotate with speeds of up to 0.6 m/s against or with the wind direction. Fig. 4.10 shows a cross-section through the flume with the moving bed.

Fig. 4.11 shows a plot of the surface drift velocity vs. moving bed speed for no-wind conditions and

Figure 4.10: Cross-section of the flume at the position where the LIF experiments were conducted. Note 1) the transparent moving bed that is driven by a rail system at its side, 2) the tilted glass window at the outer side of the channel to avoid optical distortions by a tilted optical axis.

a plot of the depth dependent induced drift. The moving bed allows for slowing down the bulk velocity and even for reversing the mean bulk flow. It is also possible to almost stop the surface drift current which is especially useful for the LIF experiments in the aqueous mass boundary layer.

For mass balance experiments but also for the oxygen quenching experiments it is necessary to degas the water in the flume. Chemical degassing techniques, e.g. using sodium nitrite and cobalt chloride cannot be used because they interfere with the oxygen quenching technique (Münsterer 1993). Degassing by conventional techniques on the other hand is time costly due to the water volume of 800 to 1000 l. Therefore a hollow fiber membrane unit by Membrane Corp. Minneapolis, Minnesota, was installed allowing for degassing to 1/10 of the equilibrium concentration in approximately two hours (see fig. 4.12). This is done by bypassing the flume water through the hollow fiber membrane unit with 12000 l/h. Gases can diffuse through the membrane surface but water cannot. The interior of the fibers is attached to a cold trap¹ and a membrane vacuum pump². Technical details of hollow fiber modules and oxygen transfer results are given in (Weiss and Gulliver 1995).

¹Necessary to keep an excess of condensing water vapor from reaching the vacuum pump.

²The membrane pump reaches a vacuum pressure of less than 100 mbar

Figure 4.11: *Left: Depth dependent drift velocity induced by different moving bed velocities: a) 33.8 cm/s, b) 29.4 cm/s, c) 24.1 cm/s, d) 18.1 cm/s and e) 13.5 cm/s. Right: induced surface drift vs. velocity of the moving bed. (from (Hering 1996))*

Dissolved oxygen concentration in the flume water is measured with a temperature-compensated oxygen meter³ in another bypass of the water circulation system.

Figure 4.12: *Degassing from equilibrium concentration to 10% of equilibrium concentration in the Heidelberg facility.*

For the Heidelberg flume extensive measurements of gas exchange rates and of the relation between wind speed and friction velocity were made by several authors. For a smooth as well as a wavy interface (Kandlbinder 1994) made measurements of the water sided friction velocity, u_* , vs. wind speed. He measured the friction velocity with the so called momentum balance method. This technique assumes that for a stationary state the momentum input into the water has to be equal to the momentum loss at the channel walls and bottom. Turning off the wind and measuring

³YSI Model 57, YSI Inc., Yellow Springs, OH

the relaxation time of the current velocity gives a proportionality constant between the current velocity and u_* . Once this constant is determined u_* can be measured by measuring the bulk current velocity in the channel. In consistency with earlier results by (Bösinger 1986) (Kandlbinder 1994) found that the friction velocity increases linearly with wind speed for an interface without waves. If waves are present the dependency can be described by a 2nd order polynomial. The values of the respective fitting functions were used for calculating u_* in the following chapters.

Figure 4.13: Friction velocity in water, u_* , as measured with the momentum balance method as a function of wind speed (Kandlbinder 1994). The dotted lines show the plausibility range of the fitted curves.

Note that the measurements by (Kandlbinder 1994) and (Bösinger 1986) do not cover the use of the moving bed. The momentum balance assumptions might change when an additional velocity difference between the moving bed and the channel walls exists. Nevertheless this possibility was neglected in this work.

4.2.1 Combined oxygen quenching/fluorescein experiments

For comparing the two laser-induced-fluorescence techniques a combined setup was built. The goal was to be able to visualize a two-dimensional concentration field with *fluorescein* and a one-dimensional oxygen concentration profile at the same time at the same place. The combined laser and imaging optical arrangement was mounted on a single base plate. Fig. 4.14 shows the experimental setup at the circular wind/wave flume of the University of Heidelberg. The experiments were done together with Hans-Jürgen Mayer.

Figure 4.14: Sketch of the combined oxygen quenching/fluorescein LIF experimental setup with imaging CCD-cameras and laser optics. The laser beams and the imaging system are combined and divided by a dichroic mirror red and blue, respectively. The complete optical setup is tilted approximately 6° to the horizontal to avoid distortion by adhesion effects at the window. The cameras as well as the laser optics are mounted on a single mounting base.

The oxygen concentration profile across the aqueous mass boundary layer was imaged with a standard NTSC camera (Sony XC-75). The PBA fluorescence was stimulated by a focused nitrogen laser beam at 337 nm wavelength with a spot diameter of $200 \mu\text{m}$. (For an implementation of a two-dimensional imaging technique with the fluorescence quenching cf. (Duke and Hanratty 1995) and (Duke 1996)). The pulse rate of the laser was 15 Hz resulting in exposure of every fourth field of the standard NTSC video frames. By averaging over the width of the laser beam, each exposed field resulted in a one-dimensional profile. Horizontal averaging further reduced the noise level. Juxtaposed sequential profiles resulted in a space-time image. The optical resolution of the

imaging system for the oxygen profiles was measured to be in the order of $24\ \mu\text{m}$ in the vertical dimension. The fluorescence spectra of *fluorescein* and *PBA* were separated using a dichroic mirror in the imaging optical path. To avoid distortions by the much brighter *fluorescein* fluorescence it was also necessary to block any remaining *fluorescein* fluorescent light with two blue low-pass filters in front of the CCD camera. Fig. 4.15 shows the transmission coefficients for the dichroic mirrors and the blue low-pass filters.

Figure 4.15: Transmission coefficients of the dichroic mirrors and the blue filter used in the combined setup. The values were taken from the data sheet by Edmund Scientific.

Fluorescence for the *fluorescein* experiment was stimulated by the focused beam of a 1 W argon ion laser⁴ (wavelength 488 nm) piercing the water surface perpendicularly from above. To investigate a two dimensional area the beam is scanned, resulting in a light sheet 6 mm wide and $60\ \mu\text{m}$ deep. Scanning the beam instead of widening it helps to avoid motion blur. Images of the concentration profiles were taken with a digital camera⁵ at a rate of 200 frames per second. The spatial resolution of the optical system was measured to be approx. $16\ \mu\text{m}$.

A second dichroic mirror allowed the beams from the two lasers to travel the same optical path as they strike the water surface. An inverted Galilean telescope optic was used to focus the two laser beams to the water surface.

Line and edge response of the optical system as well as a spot diagram were calculated in the same way as described for the setup at the University of Illinois (fig. 4.16 and fig. 4.17). Due to the tilting angle of 6° the air-glass-water interface introduces astigmatic aberrations. Since the tilting angle is lower than the one used for the experiments at the UIUC a better resolution of approx. $16\ \mu\text{m}$ can be achieved. This is the same as the pixel size of the CCD.

⁴American Laser Corp., Salt Lake City, UT

⁵Dalsa CA-D1, Dalsa Corp., Waterloo, Ontario, Canada

Figure 4.16: *Line and edge response diagram for the optical system. This plot shows how an ideal line or an ideal edge are imaged on the CCD. Digitization effects on the CCD are not considered here.*

For the experiments a stock solution of *PBA* and *fluorescein* in a NaOH solution was prepared. This stock solution was then diluted in the flume to give concentrations of 2×10^{-5} M for each of the dyes. In the flume HCl was added to titrate the solution to the *fluorescein* buffer point at pH 6.5 (Guyot *et al.* 1975). The surfactant Triton X-100 was used in a 5×10^{-6} M dilution to suppress waves in these first experiments. Triton X-100 is a highly water soluble surfactant commonly used for gas exchange studies with surfactants (cf. e.g. (Frew *et al.* 1995)). Triton X-100 did not show any interference with either of the LIF techniques. At the beginning of the experiment the water was degassed with the hollow fiber unit. The bulk concentration of oxygen in the flume was reduced to less than 1 mg/l down from the equilibrium concentration (approx. 8.5 mg/l).

Figure 4.17: Spot diagram of the optical setup. If not explicitly expressed all length values are in μm . The optical axis is only tilted 6° versus the horizontal. Therefore the optical distortions are significantly lower than those for the setup at the University of Illinois. The optical resolution of the system is approx. $16\ \mu\text{m}$, which is also the pixel size of the CCD camera. The black circle denotes the theoretical diffraction limit.

4.2.2 Measurements at a Wavy interface with an Optical Wave Follower

Measurements at a wavy interface in the Heidelberg flume are significantly more complicated than in the flume at the University of Illinois. In Heidelberg waves can reach peak-to-peak heights of 10 cm even for moderate wind speeds. To keep the water surface, i.e. the measuring section, in the imaging range of 4 by 4 mm a wave follower had to be designed. In the literature only wave following devices with a periodic input signal or driven by capacity wave height gauges (*Cheung and Street* 1986) can be found. An optically driven wave follower with a scanning mirror in the optical path of the imaging CCD camera was first constructed by (*Münsterer* 1993). Due to optical distortions this wave follower was only capable of following waves with a peak-to-peak height of less than 5 cm at an optical resolution of approximately 30 μm . It was the goal to increase the range of wave heights as well as the optical resolution by a factor of two.

Wave follower with a linear positioning table

The optical distortions in the setup by (*Münsterer* 1993) were mainly caused by imaging rays being off axis more than 3° . Therefore a first approach was to replace the scanning mirror by a static mirror and mount the complete setup on a fast linear positioning table. Fig. 4.18 shows a sketch of this setup. The linear positioning table was driven by a microstep motor⁶. As was done in the scanning approach the wave height was detected by a line array camera mounted on the opposite side of the imaging camera looking at the water surface under a 30° angle from above. The signal from this line array camera was passed to a PIC micro-controller that was programmed and adapted for this purpose by Prof. Thomas Wais of the Berufsakademie Mosbach. The micro-controller was programmed in such a way that it accelerated and retarded the microstep motor close to its maximum torque. This maximum acceleration was calculated from the mass that had to be moved and the given maximum torque and gear size. Although this was done almost ideally the system was not capable of following the waves adequately. The reason for this lies in system inherent features of any stepping motors. These motors can move to a position with an extremely high accuracy at a very fast speed. When they reach this position they have a tendency to oscillate around this new position for some milliseconds. If a step pulse is applied during this time the step motor might "loose" impulses or even worse drift into an uncontrollable state. This can only be avoided by slowing down the repetition rate of the positioning signals or the step rate. Both of these measures also slow down the system which is then no longer capable of following the waves. Another problem with this specific kind of wave follower is that it is completely position controlled, i.e. the microstep motor always tries to follow the position measured at t with retardation down to a complete stop and re-acceleration to full speed when the position at $t + 1$ comes in. For fast changes, i.e. for steep waves this leads to extremely rough following characteristics forcing many constraints on the mechanical stability of the optical system. In contrast to this the relaxation

⁶Daedal Digiplan Microstep Motor

time of a scanning mirror is in the same order of magnitude as the position signal rate. This leads to inherently smooth following characteristics. A solution for these problems could be to replace the microstep motor by a strong DC motor with a position control device in a feed back loop.

Figure 4.18: *Test setup at the circular wind/wave facility at the University of Heidelberg with a linear positioning table. In addition to the setup for a flat interface the wave follower is realized with a microstep motor driven linear positioning table. A line array camera is mounted on the other side of the flume picturing the point where the laser beam hits the water surface. This signal drives the electronics for the microstep motor. Due to technical difficulties this wave follower did not work adequately.*

Wave follower with a scanning mirror

For time reasons a different approach was preferred to a reconstruction of the linear positioning table system. The wave follower was again built with a scanning mirror in the optical path.

To avoid optical distortions caused by the scanning mirror in the optical path of the imaging CCD a so called f-theta objective was used instead of one of the achromatic lenses. The f-theta objective

Figure 4.19: Schematic showing how the focal plane of an achromatic lens differs from the object plane (from (Münsterer 1993)).

is also called flat field lens which describes its task quite accurately. The problem with using a scanning mirror is firstly that the focal plane is on a spherical shell instead of a flat plane and secondly optical distortions beyond a scanning angle of 3° are unacceptably high. The f-theta objective takes care of both of these problems. The focal plane is projected back on a flat field and scanning angles up to $\pm 25^\circ$ in air are acceptable.

The flume window adds an additional source of astigmatism to the optical system. This distortion is also present for the setup with the achromatic lenses but can be neglected for angles close to 90° between the major rays and the window. The astigmatism shown in fig. 4.4 for the setup at the University of Illinois is also caused by this effect. To gain a better understanding of these optical distortions spot diagram calculations for this specific case were done by the manufacturer of the f-theta lens⁷. Fig. 4.21 shows the ray tracing setup with the CCD at the position numbered 16. The aperture stop (no. 11) is placed at an "ideal" position with a diameter of 16 mm. Both the f-theta objective as well as the achromatic lens have a nominal focal length of 250 mm. Figure 4.22 shows the spot diagrams for different scanning angles. The astigmatism can be clearly seen but for scanning heights below ± 50 mm in the water (i.e. a peak-to-peak wave height of less than 10 cm) the rms radiuses are below $25 \mu\text{m}$. Comparing this with the calculations of the optical setups with a static mirror leads to the conclusion that the resolution of this optical system is between the one used at the University of Illinois and the one used at the University of Heidelberg. The resolution was further improved by decreasing the optical stop diameter from 16 mm to 12 mm.

All the above calculations assume that the optical axis is perpendicular to the air-glass-water interface, i.e. to the flume window. As described in the previous chapters the optical axis has to be tilted approximately 8° to avoid shading of wave troughs in the optical path. Using the standard window would have introduced an additional source of optical blur. Therefore the window was also tilted 8° against the vertical. To avoid flow distortion in the flume a window frame with a smoothed shape was manufactured and built into the Heidelberg flume (see fig. 4.10). With this tilted window the optical distortions calculated by Rodenstock should give a fairly good estimate of the real distortion in the used setup.

The image acquisition with the digital camera and a XPi860 board is the same as for the earlier setups at the University of Illinois and at the Institute for Environmental Physics. The water surface position is imaged by a line array camera on the inside of the flume. From a position above the water surface this camera images the point where the laser beam penetrates into the water. The output signal of this line array camera is directed to an adjustable comparator thresholding the wave height signal. This comparator gives a 0 V signal for rows read out of the array before a peak was detected. When the intensity peak associated with the fluorescence signal of the laser beam is detected the output signal switches to a positive TTL high signal. For a more elaborate look on the electronics of this system see (*Münsterer* 1993). This TTL signal is connected to a data acquisition board⁸ in a second PC. This data acquisition board was programmed by Dirk

⁷F-Theta Ronar by Optische Werke G. Rodenstock, München, Germany

⁸Sorcus Multilab 2 data acquisition card, SORCUS Computer GmbH, Heidelberg, Germany

Figure 4.20: *Experimental setup at the circular wind/wave facility at the University of Heidelberg. In addition to the setup for a flat interface a wave following device is installed. A line array camera is mounted on the other side of the flume picturing the point where the laser beam hits the water surface. This line array camera drives a scanning mirror in the optical path of the imaging CCD camera. To avoid optical distortions the second achromatic lens is replaced by a f-theta lens.*

Figure 4.21: Setup for the ray tracing calculations done by Rodenstock. The f -theta lens has the surfaces numbered 3 through 10, the aperture stop has the numbers 11 and 12 and the achromatic lens has the surface numbers 13 through 15. The flume window has the surface numbers 1 and 2. The CCD has the surface number 16. (calculations by Optische Werke G. Rodenstock)

Figure 4.22: Spot diagrams for the optical setup in Heidelberg with the wave follower. The spots are shown in 4 quadrants each having a side length of $50\ \mu\text{m}$. The rms radius of the spots are below $25\ \mu\text{m}$ for scanning heights of less than 55 mm. (calculations by Optische Werke G. Rodenstock)

Engelmann to calculate the wave height from the incoming TTL signal and give a drive signal to

Figure 4.23: (A color plate of this figure can be found as fig. 9.1 on page 115) *View on the setup at the circular wind/wave facility at the University of Heidelberg. The top part of the picture shows the laser optics mount with the scanner. The bottom part shows the f-theta lens in its mount which also holds the scanner mirror of the wave follower. The tilted window can be seen in the red frame.*

the scanner mirror in the optical path of the imaging optics. The board was programmed to offer the possibility of switching from a direct output to a signal with cubic extrapolation of the future wave positions.

The signal flow for the wave follower setup is shown in fig. 4.24. The line array camera gives a trigger signal after every read-out event. The frequency of this signal was adjusted to 170 Hz. This trigger drives all the other equipment. A phase-locked-loop sine wave generator produces a sine wave from the line array camera trigger signal. This sine wave is needed for driving the scanner mirror in the optical path of the laser beam that is producing the light sheet. In addition to that the sine wave generator produces a trigger signal for the digital camera. The phase shift of the sine wave and the camera trigger signal can be adjusted in such a way that the frame acquisition of the camera takes place while the laser beam sweeps over the imaging area of the digital camera and of the line array camera. An external TTL trigger is used to start the synchronous image acquisition and the storage of wave height signals on the data acquisition board. The wave height storage is again synchronized with the trigger signal from the line array camera.

Figure 4.24: Signal flow for the setup with the optical wave follower. The master trigger signal comes from the line array camera. This signal is used to trigger the digital camera, the data acquisition board and the scanning mirror producing the light sheet.

Chapter 5

Image Processing

For analyzing the recorded image sequences of the concentration profiles several image processing steps have to be performed. Figure 5.1 shows an example of three raw images out of a sequence of 1800 images. The aqueous mass boundary layer at the water surface is visible as a thin dark streak in the image. For any processing step it is a prerequisite to determine the position of the water surface in the images because the data needs to be normalized with respect to the surface. After the water surface position is found a Lambert-Beer absorption correction can take place. Laser intensity fluctuations have to be corrected as well. Then statistical features can be extracted from the images. This includes the calculation of mean concentration profiles, boundary layer thickness calculations and the calculation of the local wave slope.

Figure 5.1: *Three raw images out of a sequence of 1800 images. The sequence was recorded at the circular flume of the University of Heidelberg with a wave following device at a friction velocity of $u_* = 0.75$ cm/s.*

5.1 Preprocessing – finding the water surface

For the huge amount of data, i.e. for image sequences, preprocessing can only be achieved by highly automated image processing techniques. Although the human eye can detect the boundary layer, i.e. the water surface, almost immediately from the images sophisticated image processing steps are necessary to fulfill the same task. The problems for segmentation are caused by several factors. The boundary layer can be shaded by wave troughs in the foreground or detached parts of the boundary layer can be lower in intensity than the boundary layer itself. It is a quite sophisticated task to distinguish between an artifact and the boundary layer. The algorithms even have to decide whether there is a boundary layer in the image at all.

At the water surface the concentration of the doubly charged fluorescein anions should be minimal. Therefore the simplest approach would be to search for a local minimum in each column of the image. In real images though, this method is too vulnerable to noise and it shows that the water surface is not necessarily a minimum in grey value. Therefore the search for a local minimum is not an adequate method and other approaches were tested. The main criterion used for finding the surface is the fact that the profiles are mirrored by total reflection at the water surface. This brings forward two attempts for finding the water surface:

- the water surface is a point of high local symmetry and
- a point of maximum second derivative can be expected at the water surface.

The obvious characteristics of the boundary layer give two more criteria for improving, i.e. reducing the number of possible found positions:

- The boundary layer usually extends from one side of the image to the other. Therefore the found positions have to form a smooth connected curve.
- In the mean the water surface is the darkest part, i.e. the region of lowest concentration of R^{2-} ions. The concentration has to rise from the surface to the bulk within some 10 to 40 pixels. The boundary layer appears as a rather thin streak, i.e. the thickness lies in a certain range.

None of the above criteria is capable of individually finding the water surface. Therefore a combination of all the characteristics mentioned above are used for determining the position of the water surface. The criteria are combined and weighted using a fuzzy logic approach. The following subsections give a closer look at each of the different techniques and finally at computation time considerations and the implementation of the fuzzy logic.

5.1.1 Symmetry filtering

Caused by total reflection the original concentration profiles appear mirrored at the water surface. Therefore at the water surface a maximum of local symmetry has to be found. This is also true for a wavy interface, i.e. for an undulated mirror surface. For any wave shape the symmetry is fulfilled if the curvature of the wave at the point of the optical measuring section is not too high. For a slowly spatially changing wave slope the symmetry criterion is independent of wave slope in any direction.

In optical feature extraction methods for finding symmetry in a certain scene are well known (*Chiou and Yeh 1990*). Nevertheless these techniques are based on purely optical processing of the scene. In digital image processing most techniques for finding symmetry are used with contour lines of objects (cf. (*Brady and Asada 1984*)). This is especially true in the areas of robotics and feature reconstruction. Some later approaches also deal with symmetries of grey value images. Unfortunately most of these algorithms are very time consuming. Nevertheless some ideas by a paper of (*Zabrodsky et al. 1995*) who give a general definition of a measure of symmetry are included here. The implementation of this measure for mirror symmetry will be described further down in this section. The problem of time consuming calculations remains with all the approaches found in the literature. A possible solution are point symmetric filters that are used for analyzing one dimensional spectra, e.g. in analytical chemistry and high energy physics (*Savitzky and Golay 1964*). In the simplest case the spectrum is convolved with a filter that has a constant positive value on one side and a constant negative value of the same magnitude on the other side. For a constant grey value a convolution with this filter gives a zero response. Approaching a point of high symmetry the filter crosses through a region of large local asymmetry and responds a large value. At a point of high symmetry the filter has a zero crossing. Unfortunately such a box filter has significant disadvantages like the unpredictable smoothing properties and the fact that points further away from the point of local symmetry are given equal weight compared to the points close by. The same is true for the convolution with point symmetric filters of odd order polynomials proposed by (*Savitzky and Golay 1964*) and (*Madden 1978*).

To overcome the drawbacks of the other solutions the approach suggested here is to convolve the image with a Gaussian filter that was inverted at its center. This mask has similar properties as the point symmetric box filter: for a constant grey value this filter gives a zero response. At a point of high symmetry the filter has a steep zero crossing. The direction of this zero crossing indicates whether the point of high symmetry is a local minimum or maximum. The Gaussian mask was chosen for its predictable behavior in Fourier space (fig. 5.2). The transfer function shows that the low wave numbers are suppressed because they lie outside of the mask's range. In contrast to the box filter the "Gaussian" symmetry filter also shows predictable smoothing properties on the result. For the boundary layer images Gaussian curves with σ -values that correspond to the anticipated thickness of the boundary layer were used. For a flat interface a value of $\sigma = 12$ and for a wavy interface of $\sigma = 8$ was used. The number of coefficients was chosen to be 81. For computation time

Figure 5.2: The left hand graph shows the symmetry filter used here with a Gaussian $\sigma = 8$ (solid line) and a box filter (dashed line). The right hand side shows the transfer functions of the symmetry filter (solid line) used here and of the box symmetry filter (dashed line).

reasons convolutions with filters of such a large size are usually done in Fourier space (cf. section 5.1.4).

This symmetry filter gives zero crossings not only at points of high symmetry but also at certain step functions that are larger than the symmetry mask. At this point the measure of the "amount" of symmetry defined by (Zabrodsky *et al.* 1995) is used. Each shape P is represented by a sequence of n points $\{P_i\}_{i=-n+1}^0$, where n is the assumed spatial range of symmetry. To obtain the perfectly symmetric shape \hat{P} the points P_i are mirrored at $i = 0$. The symmetry distance (SD) is defined as the spatial distance between the actual values with positive index i , $\{P_i\}_{i=0}^{n-1}$, and its symmetry transform, \hat{P} :

$$SD = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \|P_i - \hat{P}_i\|^2$$

This is to say that SD is the minimum squared distance required to move points of the original shape in order to obtain the ideally symmetrical shape. Fig. 5.4 shows an example of a line profile that is assumed to be symmetric around the position $m = 8$. The original grey values are marked with filled dots. The ideally symmetric profile is given by the open squares. For a given $n = 6$ the symmetry distance is $3/2$. To perform such calculations for the entire image with large values for n is very time consuming. Nevertheless for an already limited number of possible points of high local symmetry found with the convolution symmetry filter it is a very efficient way to make sure that a certain point is really a point of high local symmetry and not an artifact. For good signal-to-noise ratios the symmetry distance is also very efficient in correcting the possible surface position.

Figure 5.7 shows the behavior of a surface finding filter using an additional symmetry distance criterion to verify and correct the found surface positions. For good signal-to-noise ratios the symmetry distance algorithm improves the performance of the surface finding procedure significantly. For bad signal-to-noise ratios on the other hand the performance is worse than the one of the

Figure 5.3: *Raw image and a cross section at column 100. The lower plot shows the result of symmetry filtering and the found surface position (dashed line). The reflection in the top part of the raw image also causes a steep zero crossing and has to be suppressed by other methods².*

simple convolution for finding the surface position. This means that at this point the usage of the symmetry distance criterion is useful for fluorescein image sequences but not for oxygen quenching space time images.

5.1.2 Second derivative finder

As can be seen from the theoretical profiles in figure 5.5 a total reflection of the concentration profile at the water surface causes a sharp edge at the water surface. This leads to a maximum in the second derivative in every row of the image.

Usual 2^{nd} derivative filters are very noise sensitive. This can be avoided by applying a multi-grid approach. Such a multi-grid edge detection algorithm was proposed by (*Canny* 1986). Unfortunately his algorithm involves time consuming computations. A recursive implementation of this filter with only 14 operations per output element was shown by (*Deriche* 1990). In this recursive implementation the size of the filter, i.e. its resolution and therefore the smoothing properties can

²The structure in the upper part of the image is an artifact caused by contrast enhancement for printing.

Figure 5.4: Example of calculating the symmetry distance. A line profile is assumed to be symmetric around the position $m = 8$. The original grey values are marked with filled dots. The ideally symmetric profile is given by the open squares. For a given $n = 6$ the symmetry distance is $9/6 = 3/2$.

Figure 5.5: Plot of a mean profile similar to the prediction of all theories mirrored at the water surface. At the water surface a maximum in the second derivative should occur.

be adjusted by changing a single parameter in the calculation. An example of the application of the second derivative finder on a boundary layer picture is shown in fig. 5.6.

Figure 5.6: *Raw image and a cross section at column 100. The lower plot shows the result of Canny/Deriche filtering and the found surface position (dashed line). Note that the surface position is only a local and not a global maximum of the response.*

5.1.3 Vulnerability to noise

Figure 5.7 shows a comparison of simulated results of the vulnerability to noise of different methods for finding the water surface. For simulating an image an ideal profile with an exponential shape was created and normal distributed noise was added to this profile. The signal-to-noise ratio in the plot was calculated as the ratio of the profile's concentration difference ΔC , i.e. the difference in grey value for pixel 256 and for the pixels below pixel 200, to the standard deviation of the noise distribution σ_{noise} ($S/N = \Delta C / \sigma_{noise}$). The different algorithms are then applied to this image and the standard deviation of the difference between the found surface position and the original position is plotted versus S/N.

The graph shows that the symmetry criterion is the least vulnerable to high noise levels. On the other hand it shows an almost constant deviation even for minute noise levels. This is caused by

Figure 5.7: Reliability of the different surface finding methods exposed to different signal-to-noise ratios. The standard deviation of the difference between the actual and the found surface position is given versus the signal-to-noise ratio.

the large number of coefficients of the mask (81 coefficients). The Canny/Deriche filter shows a somewhat larger increase with noise but starting at zero deviation for high signal-to-noise ratios. As expected the simplest criterion by finding only local minima shows the worst overall performance. This simulation does not cover "real image effects" like bubbles, dirt or the possibility of finding a wrong surface position. Tests showed that the local minima finder is the most vulnerable to all of these effects. The Canny/Deriche filter is the most resistant to these effects. Nevertheless in contrast to the mean concentration profiles an instantaneous profile does not necessarily have to show a sharp edge at the surface. Such an effect can only be detected by the symmetry operator.

5.1.4 Computation time considerations

The convolution of an image G with a filter H in object space is equivalent to the complex multiplication of the Fourier transformed image \hat{G} with the Fourier transformed filter \hat{H} and the back transformation of the result. The one-dimensional symmetry filter is only Fourier transformed once for the complete sequence and then multiplied with the Fourier transformation of every image line. The result is transformed back to image space. Therefore the computational effort per image consists of a one-dimensional Fourier transformation of the image, one multiplication for each pixel and a back transformation of the resulting image. For a 256×256 pixel image such a convolution in Fourier space takes a computation time of approx. 0.24s on a 90 MHz Pentium computer. The direct convolution in object space would take approx. 0.54s. The calculation of the recursive Canny/Deriche filter for finding the second derivative takes about 0.06s on the same computer.

Figure 5.8: The cross section at column 143 of this image shows that in real images the water surface is not necessarily a local minimum of the grey values. The assumed surface position is marked with an arrow.

5.1.5 Fuzzy logic

Most systems in the area of decision making are highly non-linear in their connection of input and output variables. An alternative to a deterministic model is a fuzzy logic approach (Zadeh 1978). Fuzzy set theory has found a large number of applications over the last years. This is because fuzzy logic is a rational way of representing human thinking (Mamdani 1977). In fuzzy logic the unknown function relating the input to the output parameters is approximated. For this approximation fuzzy logic does not need an exact mathematical description but is able to be trained from examples. It has the advantage that input variables can be expressed within a certain range of variability. For example a section of a line does not have to be either long or short, but can be a little bit of both and mainly medium in length. These so called linguistic input variables are combined with a so called rule base. The result of this rule base is then defuzzified, i.e. converted back to a simple yes or no argument. A more thorough description of an application of fuzzy logic to image sequence analysis is given in (Haußecker 1994).

Input variables for the fuzzy logic

The output of the symmetry finder and the second derivative finder are not used as direct input into the fuzzy logic algorithm. The reason for this is that the response of both filters is highly dependent on image contrast. There are better characteristics of the concentration profile images that are almost independent of grey value. The characteristics used are:

- the *length* of a connected region in the image,

- the *thickness* of a potential boundary layer,
- the variance of the found positions from a smoothed curve, the *smoothness*, and
- the *separation* from the position found in this column from the one found in the previous column.

Length: For calculating the length the binary image with the possible found positions is dilated with a 5×5 mask that has a V shape in direction of propagation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

This results in regions that are connected even if the position information is lost for up to 4 rows. These regions are then labeled and the extension from the left to the right side of the image is determined for each region.

Thickness: The grey value at the possible position is called c_i . The difference in grey value between a possible water surface position and the next local maximum in a certain range is denoted Δc . The thickness is measured as the distance between the found position and the position where the grey value reaches $c_i + (1/e \times \Delta c)$. Neglecting Lambert-Beer absorption at this point this definition is equivalent to the defined boundary layer thickness of an ideal exponential profile. The problem with this definition is that points close to a grey value edge in an artifact yield smaller, i.e. better thickness values. To avoid biasing towards edge regions the thickness value is calculated as the root mean square value in direction of the original profile and its mirror image. This definition favors symmetric water surface points.

Smoothness: For calculating the smoothness value the position values labeled in a connected region are smoothed with a binary filter of size 16. This operation suppresses small fluctuations in the water surface position. The smoothness is defined as the squared difference between the smoothed and the original position value. These values are again smoothed with a binary filter to get an estimate of the smoothness in a certain range.

Separation: The separation is defined as the position difference between the position accepted for previous column and the suggested position in this column.

Fuzzifier

The fuzzifier consists of a predefined set of membership functions, the so called linguistic variables. They denote the amount of activation of the investigated property. As mentioned above in the application here the linguistic variables are:

- *length* of the boundary layer,
- *thickness* of the boundary layer,
- *smoothness* of the possible surface positions and
- *separation* from the position accepted in the previous line.

Each of these linguistic variables can have a certain degree of activation of its properties *Small*, *Medium* and *Large*. The optimized linguistic variables are shown in fig. 5.9.

Figure 5.9: *Optimized linguistic variables for length, thickness, separation, and smoothness.*

For a length value of 50 the linguistic variable *Small Length* is activated to a degree of 0.82. The linguistic variable *Medium Length* is activated to a degree of 0.34 and *Large Length* is activated to a degree of 0.25 for a length of 50. Note that the sum of activation at a certain point does not have to be unity. Degrees of activation denote a "possibility", not a probability (Zadeh 1978).

For every possible water surface position in the LIF images a set of values for the length, the thickness of the boundary layer, the smoothness of the curve and the separation from the accepted

		THICKNESS <i>thin</i>			THICKNESS <i>medium</i>			THICKNESS <i>thick</i>		
		SMO <i>small</i>	SMO <i>medium</i>	SMO <i>far</i>	SMO <i>small</i>	SMO <i>medium</i>	SMO <i>far</i>	SMO <i>small</i>	SMO <i>medium</i>	SMO <i>far</i>
LEN <i>short</i>	SEP <i>small</i>	medium	low	low	low	low	low	low	low	low
	SEP <i>medium</i>	low	low	low	low	low	low	low	low	low
	SEP <i>large</i>	low	low	low	low	low	low	low	low	low
LEN <i>medium</i>	SEP <i>small</i>	high	high	medium	medium	low	low	low	low	low
	SEP <i>medium</i>	low	low	low	low	low	low	low	low	low
	SEP <i>large</i>	low	low	low	low	low	low	low	low	low
LEN <i>long</i>	SEP <i>small</i>	very high	high	high	high	medium	medium	low	low	low
	SEP <i>medium</i>	medium	low	low	medium	low	low	low	low	low
	SEP <i>large</i>	medium	low	low	low	low	low	low	low	low

Table 5.1: Rule table for the fuzzy logic implementation. **SEP** stands for the separation from the previously found position, **SMO** for the smoothness of the found positions and **LEN** for the length of a connected region.

position in the previous column is determined. This is done independently for the results of the symmetry finder and the 2nd derivative filter.

For computation time reasons the linguistic variables are not recalculated for every value. Instead every possible integer input value between 0 and 256 is stored in a look-up table. Hence the table for each linguistic variable consists of 3 columns (Small, Medium and Large) and 257 rows.

Rule base

The rule base consists of IF ... THEN ... type of rules which connect the linguistic variables. The rule base establishes the relationship between the input and the output set. The structure of the rule base is based on a priori knowledge of the systems behavior. For example if a possible boundary layer position is 256 pixels long, has a boundary layer thickness of 10 pixels, is smooth and leads to a connected curve the "possibility" of a correct position is *Very High*. The membership values of the defuzzifier are *Low*, *Medium*, *High* and *Very High*.

All unique combinations of the degree of membership for each fuzzy set for each input measure are

combined via a fuzzy "AND" and a fuzzy "OR":

$$AND : (a_n \wedge b_l) \rightarrow \min(a_n, b_l), \quad (5.1)$$

$$OR : (a_n \vee b_l) \rightarrow \max(a_n, b_l), \quad (5.2)$$

that use the MINIMUM OF ... and the MAXIMUM OF ... operations instead of the Boolean operations. For every combination of input variables a_n and b_l the AND operator (5.1) gives a measure for the possibility of a certain combination c_m :

$$c_m = a_n \wedge b_l. \quad (5.3)$$

Since more than one combination of input variables is assigned to one output variable (e.g. 5 combinations result in the output possibility *High*) the combinations resulting in a single output variable C_m are combined with an OR operator (5.2).

$$C_m = \bigvee_{n,l \in \mathcal{M}} (a_n \wedge b_l), \quad \mathcal{M} = \{(n, l) : A_n \wedge B_l = C_m\} \quad (5.4)$$

The combination rules, the so called rule base is shown in table 5.1.5. For example a possible position with a *long Length*, a *small Separation*, a *small Smoothness* and a *medium Thickness* value has a *high* output value.

The membership values of the linguistic output variables are contained in the vector

$$\vec{C}_m = \{C_{m,Low}, C_{m,Medium}, C_{m,High}, C_{m,VeryHigh}\}.$$

Defuzzifier

The fuzzy set activates each linguistic output variable C_m to a certain degree. A single control value u is evaluated of each vector \vec{C}_m by the defuzzification. The control output may be represented by the relationship $u = g(\vec{C}_m)$, where g is the defuzzification function (Athalye *et al.* 1993). Different defuzzification schemes are used in the literature. The simplest method is to use the maximum value of the activations. This method is called *maximum-membership defuzzification*. Nevertheless this strategy has certain disadvantages: it is possible that the control value u is not unique and the output variable tends to jump instead of interpolate between different possibilities. Therefore the modification of an alternative method is used here, the so called *fuzzy centroid defuzzification* scheme. The output value u is calculated as the center of mass of the area under the defuzzification curves activated to a certain degree $C_{m,Ling}$. The upper part of fig. 5.10 shows the defuzzification function used. The bottom part gives an example of how the control value u is calculated from the input vector $\vec{C} = \{C_{Low} = 0, C_{Medium} = 0, C_{High} = 0.5, C_{VeryHigh} = 0.2\}$.

If the resulting control value is above a certain threshold the position might be accepted as a water surface position. If there is more than one accepted value in a column the position with the highest corresponding control value is selected. If none of the control values is above the threshold no position is marked for this column. This can be the case if the boundary layer is shaded by wave troughs in the foreground or for bad signal-to-noise ratios.

Figure 5.10: *Upper part: optimized defuzzification function. Bottom part: example of how the control value u is calculated from the input vector $\vec{C} = \{C_{Low} = 0, C_{Medium} = 0, C_{High} = 0.5, C_{VeryHigh} = 0.2\}$.*

Optimization procedure

The shapes of the linguistic variables h were optimized using 20 example images. In these images the actual position of the water surface y_i was given interactively. A performance index J is defined as the sum of the squared distances between the given and the position found by the fuzzy set r_i .

$$J = \sum_{image=1}^{image \leq 20} \sum_{row=0}^{row \leq 255} (y_{image,column} - r_{image,column})^2 \quad (5.5)$$

The best possible set of linguistic variable shapes have to minimize J :

$$J(h(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)) \rightarrow \text{Min.} \quad (5.6)$$

This is a special case of a general optimization problem. A solution was found with the simplex method (*Numerical Recipes* 1992). It is observed that there are no equality or inequality constraints in this formulation. The constraints, e.g. that the shapes of the linguistic variables have to overlap, are included in the algorithm as a "penalty function" (*Athalye et al.* 1993). If the new set of coordinates violates the given constraints the performance index J is set to a fixed very high value.

To start the optimization procedure for the n coordinate values $n + 1$ random coordinate sets have to be created. Obviously these random coordinate sets have to fulfill the constraints. For each of these coordinate sets the performance index is calculated. These coordinate sets and the corresponding performance indexes are used as input for the simplex algorithm from (*Numerical Recipes* 1992).

The result of this optimization is shown in figs. 5.9 and 5.10. It did not prove useful to optimize all the possible coordinate sets. For example it is of major importance that the found curve is connected and does not display steps. On the other hand not all coordinates are independent of each other. The output coordinates influence the value of the threshold value below which the control value u is accepted or rejected. Therefore the coordinate sets for the linguistic variables *separation* and *smoothness* as well as the threshold value were given as fixed values. The number of coordinates that needed to be optimized was 24. To minimize the chance of finding a local minimum for the performance index several runs with different random coordinate sets were performed.

5.2 Calibration and correction

After the water surface position is found the correction and calibration steps can take place. For the setup at the University of Heidelberg where the laser beam penetrates the water surface from above a Lambert-Beer absorption takes place along the profile starting at the water surface. Absorption correction can only be performed after the water surface is found and the image is shifted to the frame of reference of the moving water surface. For this an exponential fit is done for 20 out of the 1800 randomly chosen images and the mean coefficient is used for the correction. This is automatically done for every image in the sequence.

Since the laser light sheet is produced by a scanning laser beam the intensity of the light sheet is not homogeneous over the image. The intensity usually has the shape of a cosine function having a higher value at the boundaries and a minimum in the middle. Although the digital camera used has a rather low noise level it displays a non-static intensity pattern along the columns. Figure 5.11 shows an example image and a cross-section through this image along row 200. These effects can be corrected if a region in the bulk is taken as a normalization base, i.e. the average for 20 rows along each column is used for scaling the complete column. This is only possible because the concentration and therefore the light intensity in the bulk can be assumed constant. Fluctuations of the laser intensity are also corrected normalizing with a region far apart from the boundary layer.

Figure 5.11: *Example image after shifting and Lambert-Beer correction. The image on the left is without intensity correction, the image on the right hand side with intensity correction. The cross-sections at row 200 show the influence of the intensity correction.*

5.3 Calculation of statistical properties

5.3.1 Mean concentration profiles

After the images have been brought into the frame of reference of the moving water surface and correction has taken place statistical properties can be extracted. The *mean concentration profiles* are calculated by taking the average over all images. Areas where no water surface position could be found are set to zero before the averaging process. The water surface position cannot be found if the boundary layer is shaded by wave troughs in the foreground or if the signal-to-noise ratio is

to small. This is especially the case for an air-sided HCl flux that is too small at this moment.

From the mean concentration profiles the *mean boundary layer thickness*, z_* , is calculated. This is done in two ways:

1. If the boundary layer thickness is significantly bigger than the resolution of the optical system, the tangent to the profiles at the point of maximum slope is taken. This tangent intersects the water surface coordinate at the point with the concentration $c_{surface}$. The boundary layer thickness is then calculated as $z_* = \frac{c_{bulk} - c_{surface}}{slope}$. The procedure is shown schematically in fig. 5.12. This point of maximum slope will usually not be directly at the water surface but 30 to 40 μm further down in the bulk. This is most probably caused by the limited resolution which causes a flattening of the steep concentration peak (cf. fig. 5.5).
2. If the boundary layer thickness is comparable to the optical resolution a different approach has to be taken. The concentration profiles are fitted with an exponential function. For this fitting process the first 3 values are ignored because they are mostly affected by the optical blur. The use of an exponential function is justified by the fact that a concentration profile with a Schmidt number exponent of 1/2 can be expected for very thin boundary layers.

Figure 5.12: Schematic showing how the boundary layer thickness and the bulk and surface concentrations are found applying a tangent to the point of maximum slope in the mean concentration profile.

Both procedures yield good results in the range of thicknesses where they are applicable. The tangent method fails for boundary layers that are too thin. On the other hand the exponential fit

fails for boundary layers with thicknesses that are still subject to Schmidt number exponent $2/3$ profiles (cf. fig. 2.5 on page 17).

The exponential fit will bias the shape of the normalized profiles towards an exponential shape. This is caused by the fact that both scaling parameters, the concentration difference as well as the boundary layer thickness, are determined by this fit. However the bias will not distort the profile's shape completely. The major difference between the predictions by the small eddy and the surface renewal model is that the small eddy model profile decreases much slower towards the bulk concentration. This is an effect in the order 10% which cannot be changed by simple scaling.

5.3.2 Local boundary layer thicknesses

The local boundary layer thicknesses in the images is calculated very similar to the procedure used for the input parameters of the fuzzy logic. The difference is that the resolution is limited by smoothing the image to suppress higher frequency changes. Fulfilling the sampling theorem the resolution is reduced from 256 to 32 values, i.e. reduction by a factor of 8. At this level the thickness is measured as the distance between the found water surface position and the position where the grey value reaches $c_{surface} + (1/e \times \Delta c)$. Δc denotes the difference in grey values between the water surface and the bulk. In contrast to the calculation of the fuzzy logic input parameters the thickness here is calculated only for the actual profile and not as the rms thickness for the profile and its mirror image. This method yields a fairly good estimate of boundary layer thicknesses with only small biases especially for larger thicknesses. For larger thicknesses the definition of the thickness as the $1/e$ difference value is slightly incorrect.

If an image has regions where no water surface position could be found the image is first interpolated with a so called normalized convolution (*Knudsson and Westin 1993*). This yields an image with interpolated values at the relevant positions that is already smoothed and reduced in size by a factor of 8. The thickness values at the interpolated positions are not used as a result but interpolation is necessary to avoid distortions on neighboring values in the smoothing/reduction process.

5.3.3 Local wave slope

From the images recorded at the University of Illinois a local wave slope can be extracted. This is possible because the optical system was not moving and part of a wave with the boundary layer can be seen in the image. Using the water surface position found with fuzzy logic the local wave slope can be calculated. The procedure is similar to the one used for calculating the local thickness. First regions with no water surface position are interpolated and the image is reduced to a size of 32 pixels. Then the wave slope for this reduced and smoothed set of water surface positions is calculate by convolution with a first order derivative operator with 9 elements (cf. (*Jähne 1993*)). This yields a local wave slope information that can be compared to the local boundary layer thickness information.

Chapter 6

Verification of the data

Verifying the LIF measurements is a major necessity for using these techniques in understanding the mechanisms of air-sea gas exchange. Verification on the other hand is rather complicated because the fluorescein technique as well as the oxygen quenching technique acquire information that cannot be deduced by other methods with a comparable spatial and temporal resolution. Therefore several individual steps have to be considered for verification:

- Verification of the underlying physical process: The linear or functional dependency of the fluorescence intensity with the tracer concentration was already shown in sections 3.1.3 and 3.2.
- Cross-validation: Effects like the surface renewal structures in the fluorescein images that were already reported in (*Münsterer* 1993) should be measurable with the oxygen quenching technique as well.
- Comparison with oxygen mass balance results: The mean profiles measured with the fluorescein and the oxygen quenching technique can be compared with the mean boundary layer thicknesses calculated from the parallel oxygen mass balance experiments. Although the concentration profile measurements yield a variety of additional information the mean boundary layer thickness z_* has to coincide with the one calculated from the transfer velocity measured with oxygen mass balance.

6.1 Fluorescein

Figure 6.1 shows a comparison of the boundary layer thicknesses (z_*) measured with fluorescein compared to those calculated from the oxygen invasion transfer velocities. The z_* values from the mass balance experiment were normalized to $Sc = 600$. The solid line shows the assumed Sc

Figure 6.1: Comparison of the boundary layer thicknesses measured by the fluorescein method with those calculated from the oxygen transfer velocity.

dependency for a diffusion constant for fluorescein of $D = 3.67 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$ (Hodges and La Mer 1948). This diffusion constant results in a Schmidt number of 2440 for fluorescein. Therefore the boundary layer thicknesses for fluorescein should fall on this solid line. The z_* values using NH_3 as an initiator deviate significantly from this line. The HCl values agree with this prediction within the margins of error ($\Delta z_*/z_* = 8\%$ for the oxygen mass balance value and $\Delta z_*/z_* = 5\%$ for the fluorescein value). The problem with the NH_3 probably results from the low rate constant for the dissociation reaction $\text{NH}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O} \leftrightarrow \text{NH}_4^+ + \text{OH}^-$. The combined profile is affected both by the fluorescein and NH_3 transfer. The small rate constant for NH_3 violates one of the basic assumptions for the feasibility of the fluorescein technique: the time for the protonation reaction must be small compared to any transportation processes. On the other hand this assumption is completely fulfilled for the HCl. More thorough investigations and numerical simulations have to be performed to be able to interpret the profiles obtained with NH_3 as an initiator for the fluorescein flux.

6.2 Oxygen quenching

Figure 6.2 shows a comparison of z_* values (both normalized to $\text{Sc} = 600$) for the oxygen quenching and oxygen mass balance technique first shown in (Münsterer et al. 1995). An ideal system would result in data points lying on the diagonal. The margins of error for the mass balance measurements and the oxygen quenching technique are 8% and 5%, respectively. The values agree quite well with each other, although larger differences can be seen for the values measured at 3.6 m/s wind speed.

Figure 6.2: Comparison of the boundary layer thicknesses measured by the oxygen quenching method (PBA boundary layer thickness) with those calculated from the oxygen transfer velocity (mass balance boundary layer thickness). An ideal system would result in data points lying on the diagonal. The plot also shows that gas transfer was increased by the use of the moving bed.

All of these values were measured on the same day. Therefore the deviation is probably due to a calibration problem with the oxygen probe.

The plot also shows that for a flat high shear interface the moving bed induces higher gas exchange rates. This is caused by the fact that the moving bed did not run smoothly for these experiments. The uneven run excited small "mechanical" surface waves that slightly increased gas exchange.

Chapter 7

Results and Discussion

7.1 Results for a flat interface

7.1.1 Oxygen quenching technique

Mean concentration profiles

Mean oxygen concentration profiles measured with the oxygen quenching technique were presented by (*Münsterer et al. 1995*) and (*Mayer 1995*). Two mean profiles obtained with this technique at a flat high shear interface are shown with normalized depth and concentration values in fig. 7.1. The plot also shows oxygen concentration profiles measured with oxygen micro-probes by (*Chu and Jirka 1992*) and (*Prinos et al. 1995*). They demonstrated the acquisition of mean oxygen values as well as oxygen concentration fluctuations (c') in a grid stirred tank and a jet agitated vessel, respectively. Although these authors also measured mean concentration profiles a comparison with the LIF results is difficult due to the different methods for creating turbulence. Both micro-probe experiments were carried out at a practically no-shear interface. The experiments at the circular flume of the University of Heidelberg with a flat wind driven air-water interface result in a high-shear interface. Nevertheless a simple comparison of the profile shapes shows the advantages of the non-intrusive fluorescence method. The spatial resolution is much higher and the distance between two neighboring measuring points is much lower. Another advantage of the fluorescence quenching method is the possibility of instantaneously measuring one-dimensional or even two-dimensional concentration profiles. The oxygen micro-probes are restricted to point measurements which are later combined to a mean profile.

In contrast to the profiles measured with the micro-probes the oxygen quenching profiles show a reasonable agreement with the model predictions for a Schmidt number exponent of $n = 2/3$. Nevertheless a distinction between the two models is not possible with these measurements. The

Figure 7.1: Mean oxygen concentration profiles (solid symbols) measured at a flat high shear interface at the circular wind/wave facility of the University of Heidelberg. The experiments were conducted together with Hans-Jürgen Mayer (Mayer 1995). The predictions of two gas exchange models (lines) and results of oxygen micro-probe measurements by (Chu and Jirka 1992) and (Prinos et al. 1995) (open symbols) are plotted for comparison. The profiles are not fully comparable because (Chu and Jirka 1992) measured theirs in a grid-stirred tank whereas (Prinos et al. 1995) measured theirs in a jet-agitated vessel.

reason is the extremely bad signal-to-noise ratio for single profiles which gives way to segmentation errors as described in section 5.1. Another source of error is the optical resolution which was measured to be in the order of $30 \mu\text{m}$. Optical blur affects mainly the region near the water surface which causes a bias in the determination of the boundary layer thickness. The difference between the predictions by the surface renewal and the small eddy model differ by less than 5% for a flat interface which is approximately the margin of error for the LIF measurements.

Profiles of the concentration fluctuation c'

The oxygen quenching technique offers the possibility of measuring root mean square (rms) fluctuations, c' , of the oxygen concentration in time. This is not possible with the fluorescein technique because the influence of air-side controlled HCl flux fluctuations is superimposed to the surface concentration changes. Directly measuring c' gives an additional possibility of testing mass transfer models. The small eddy model deliberately uses the assumption that the concentration fluctuations

are null at the surface (see eq. 2.24). No such assumption is made for the surface renewal model. Following the physical arguments of the surface renewal model a non-zero value of c' at the interface can be expected. When a surface renewal effect occurs at the surface, the surface concentration has to drop until air-sided diffusion can reestablish the Ostwald solubility condition.

(*Chu and Jirka 1992*) and (*Prinos et al. 1995*) both published c' profiles measured in their tanks. Although both experiments were made using oxygen micro-probes their experiments do not yield the same results. (*Chu and Jirka 1992*) interpreted their results to a decrease of the c' values close to the free surface whereas (*Prinos et al. 1995*) saw an increase of c' towards the interface. The reason might be based in the different setups or in technological problems. (*Prinos et al. 1995*) conclude from their experiments that when the interface is agitated enough (hence when horizontal eddies can develop freely), an intermittent surface renewal occurs which leads to low frequency concentration fluctuations and an increase in mass transfer. Both experiments have difficulties in assuring a constant distance of their probe from the water surface. Since these difficulties cause a smoothing or averaging effect in the measurement of mean profiles it can cause an unpredictable bias in the c' measurements.

Measuring c' values with the oxygen quenching technique has some difficulties that mainly originate in the bad signal-to-noise ratio of the measured concentration profiles. The signal-to-noise ratio is approximately 5 using the definition of S/N in section 5.1.3. To understand the behavior of LIF measurements of the c' values two sets of simulations were conducted. The first one used simulated profiles and the second one used part of an original sequence. The simulated profiles were calculated using a concentration profile of exponential shape superimposing a noise level which is comparable to the one in the actual experiments (S/N = 5). The boundary layer thickness was undulated with a sine wave. The position of the "water surface" will be found with the systematic errors caused by noise described in section 5.1.3. To get a measure for the vulnerability of the c' profiles to random segmentation errors additional segmentation errors were added. In columns where such random segmentation errors arise a bulk position is found instead of the water surface position. A careful visual analysis of the segmented surface positions in the measured profiles leads to an upper estimate of random segmentation errors below 0.5%. The c' values for the simulated profiles plotted in fig. 7.2 show a bump at a depth of $z = z_*$. This bump is caused by the fluctuating boundary layer thickness. Looking at the concentration fluctuations in a certain depth a fluctuating boundary layer thickness causes an increase in these fluctuations. At the water surface the simulated c' profile almost decreases back to its bulk value. The increase of c' at the surface caused by the systematic segmentation errors is in the order of 0.02 normalized units. Adding 1% segmentation errors only causes another increase of 0.02 normalized units.

A second set of tests was done with part of an original space-time image. Similar to the procedure for the simulated profiles additional random segmentation errors were added. Fig. 7.3 shows that these random segmentation errors cause an increase of c' close to the surface. Again this error is only in the order of 0.02 normalized units for an additional segmentation error of 1%. Therefore any increase in c' values that is above 0.04 normalized units can be ascribed to a real physical

Figure 7.2: Concentration fluctuations for a series of simulated profiles with a constant surface concentration (i.e. $c' = 0$). The noise level was adjusted to the level in the measured profiles and a slowly fluctuating boundary layer thickness was used.

effect.

Figure 7.4 shows a comparison of the c' values calculated from the oxygen quenching results with those measured by (Chu and Jirka 1992) and (Prinos et al. 1995) using oxygen micro-probes. The LIF c' profiles show a bump around a depth value of z_* . The c' value then seems to increase or at least remain on a higher level than in the bulk. The difference between the bulk c' value and the surface c' value is at least 0.1 normalized units. This is well above the increase of 0.04 normalized units which could be caused by noise and segmentation errors. The non-zero value in the bulk is caused by the noise level in the single profile measurements.

This proves that the increase of c' close to the interface is a real effect. In other words the concentration fluctuations do not cease at the water surface. This non-zero c' value at the surface is a clear contradiction to the assumptions of the small eddy model and therefore supports the surface renewal model. The bump close to the interface is caused by the fluctuating boundary layer thicknesses at a water surface exposed to high shear stress.

Single oxygen concentration profiles

A space time image of oxygen concentration profiles recorded at a friction velocity of $u_* = 0.63$ cm/s is shown in fig. 7.5. Although the noise level of these measurements is relatively high ($S/N = 5$) the fluctuating boundary layer thickness can be seen in the images.

Figure 7.3: Test for the vulnerability of concentration fluctuations to additional random segmentation errors.

Measurements of concentration profiles with the fluorescein method revealed that parts of the boundary layer were swapped into the bulk by larger eddies (cf. (Münsterer 1993) and (Münsterer *et al.* 1995)). The fluorescein technique was the only one being able to measure these effects. Therefore a verification of these surface renewal effects is necessary. The oxygen quenching method is capable of doing this cross-validation. Nevertheless the high noise level and the slow repetition rate of the profile measurements (15 Hz) which is caused by the present experimental realization makes an identification of surface renewal effects in the space time images a difficult task. Nevertheless they can be identified looking at single profiles. Figure 7.6 shows five consecutive concentration profiles at a wind speed of 4.5 m/s using the moving bed to minimize the bulk velocity of the water. The profiles are measured 1/15 of a second apart and show a fast surface renewal effect (marked with the arrow). Part of the boundary layer is swept into the bulk and for a short period the surface concentration drops significantly. It is this effect which causes the non-zero value of c' at the interface described in the above section.

The above results verify the surface renewal effects measured with the fluorescein method. On the other hand it is obvious that the signal-to-noise level of oxygen quenching measurements has to be improved. A temporal resolution of at least 15 Hz seems to be the minimum requirement for identifying fast processes like surface renewal effects.

Figure 7.4: Comparison of rms concentration fluctuations at different distances from the water surface. The same arguments used for the mean profiles apply to the comparability of the concentration fluctuations measured by LIF with those measured with oxygen micro-probes.

Figure 7.5: (A color plate of this figure can be found as fig. 9.3 on page 117) *Left: Space time image of oxygen concentration profiles of an oxygen invasion experiment at a flat interface with $u_* = 0.63$ cm/s. The aqueous mass boundary layer can be seen in bright grey values in the top part of the image. The image is converted to the frame of reference of the water surface. Right: Cross section through a single concentration profile at time $t = 8$ s.*

Figure 7.6: Oxygen concentration profiles measured at 4.5 m/s wind speed at a rate of 15 Hz. The profiles show the occurrence of a surface renewal effect which also causes a significant drop of oxygen concentration at the surface at $t = 0.133$ s. The error bars denote a 2σ range, i.e. a 95.4% confidence level of the background noise.

7.1.2 Fluorescein technique

The mean concentration profiles measured at the University of Heidelberg (IUP) for a smooth interface show the expected properties. The boundary layer thickness decreases with increasing momentum input into the water (fig. 7.7).

Figure 7.7: *Fluorescein concentration profiles measured at a smooth interface at the IUP for different wind speeds. The profiles were normalized with respect to concentration. The plot shows the decrease of the boundary layer thickness with increasing friction velocity. The profiles were averaged spatially over 230 single profiles, i.e. columns, and 1800 consecutive images. This results in an average over more than 410000 single profiles.*

The profiles form a single curve when scaled with boundary layer thickness (fig. 7.8). The profile shapes clearly show the behavior predicted by the models for a Schmidt number exponent $2/3$ regime. The mean profiles obtained with the fluorescein method at a flat interface do not differ from those measured with the oxygen quenching method (fig. 7.1).

For a flat interface the predictions by the small eddy and the surface renewal model lie too close to be distinguished with the profile measurements. This is only a technical limitation at this time. The profiles for a wavy interface differ more significantly and a difference should be feasible even with the current margin of error of approx. 5%.

Figure 7.8: Same fluorescein concentration profiles as in fig. 7.7 but normalized with boundary layer thickness. The boundary layer thickness seems to be the appropriate scaling parameter to make each profile fall on a single master curve. Although the measured profiles seem to be closer to the surface renewal model prediction the comparison between the measured profiles and the predictions by the theory cannot finally distinguish between the small eddy and the surface renewal model. The predictions of the two models for a flat interface are only 5% apart which is the margin of error for the LIF measurements.

7.2 Results for a wavy interface

7.2.1 Mean concentration profiles

Mean concentration profiles for wavy interfaces were calculated for the measurements at the University of Illinois (UIUC) and the IUP. At the IUP a wave follower was used. The profiles measured at different conditions at the UIUC are shown in fig. 7.9. The scaling parameters boundary layer thickness, z_* , and concentration difference, Δc , were calculated in the manner described in section 5.3.1. For the profiles measured at friction velocities of 1.49 to 1.41 cm/s an exponential fit was used. For the profile measured at $u_* = 1.25$ cm/s the tangent method was used. The profiles obtained at the higher friction velocities agree very well with the predictions of the surface renewal model for a Schmidt number exponent of $1/2$. This is consistent with the observation of a fully developed wave field with 3-dimensional waves. At the facility of the UIUC so called pebble waves develop at these wind speeds. For $u_* = 1.25$ cm/s the wave field was only 2-dimensional which justifies

the correspondence with the predictions for a Schmidt number exponent of $2/3$. The deviation of this profile for a depth below 2.5 normalized units is caused by problems with Lambert-Beer and intensity corrections for a tilted laser beam.

Figure 7.9: *Fluorescein concentration profiles measured at a wavy interface at the facility at the University of Illinois. All profiles are normalized with concentration difference and boundary layer thickness. The profiles show a change in Schmidt number exponent for the wavy conditions. They seem to be much closer to the predictions of the surface renewal model. (SR: surface renewal model, K: small eddy model)*

The mean profiles show flattening at the water surface between 30% and 40% of the surface concentration. This seems to be caused by deviations introduced by the optical system used in this setup (cf. section 4.1). Optical blur affects mainly the regions close to the water surface. Comparing this with the calculated line and edge responses of the optical system (fig. 4.5) explains the deviations of the first 2 to 3 pixels (32 to 48 μm).

The striking agreement of the measured concentration profiles with the predictions of the surface renewal model is partly biased by the use of the exponential fit. The fitting procedure influences the z_* value as well as the scaling parameter Δc . Cross-checking the results with a fit with the function predicted by the small eddy model is not possible. This function is too complicated for a

non-linear fitting procedure (cf. eq. 2.41). Nevertheless the shape of the curves cannot be altered completely by the scaling procedure. Even if the correspondence with the surface renewal model prediction is biased the fact remains that the concentration decrease into the bulk is much faster than predicted by the small eddy model. This indicates an enhancement of transport by larger scale eddies.

7.2.2 Dependency of boundary layer thickness on wave slope

It is possible to calculate the local wave slope and boundary layer thickness from single images recorded at the UIUC. A fixed optical system was used there. The use of the wave follower prevents this method from being applicable to the data from the IUP. The data processing procedure was described in the sections 5.3.2 and 5.3.3. Fig. 7.10 shows a plot of local boundary layer thickness versus local wave slope for a friction velocity of $u_* = 1.41$ cm/s. Here, wave slope is defined as the dimensionless derivative dy/dx . The mean boundary layer thickness values were calculated over a range of 0.04 wave slope units. They show no correlation with wave slope. The fluctuations of the single values are denoted by the error bars having the length of the Gaussian standard deviation σ . The failure of a correlation between local wave slope and local boundary layer thickness contradicts predictions made by (*Back and McCreedy 1988*). They stated that shear stress variations at a free interface cause a slope dependent transfer velocity, i.e. boundary layer thickness.

Although these measurements were conducted at the wind/wave facility of the UIUC the results seem to transferable to other facilities as well. The water height of the UIUC facility is small (1 cm) and the resulting wave field consists only of capillary waves. On the other hand results from mean square slope measurements ((*Duke 1994*) and (*Balschbach 1997*)) and gas transfer experiments (*McCreedy and Hanratty 1985*) show that the conditions are quite comparable to those of other facilities. The limited water height has the advantage that the wave field is in equilibrium even after a short fetch of only 7 m.

Since there is no direct correlation on a local level there might exist a correlation on a larger scale still in the order of magnitude of capillary waves. The experiments of the fluorescence technique with the color imaging slope gauge (CISG) allows for a comparison of wave slope fields with boundary layer profile images. A sequence of four consecutive wave slope images is shown in fig. 7.11. A steep wave train is crossing through the measuring section at time $t = 0$ ms. During the pass of this steep wave train no boundary layer images could be recorded due to shielding by wave troughs in the foreground. 33.3 ms later a first boundary layer detachment effect can be seen in the concentration profile images. At this time the local wave slope is already back to moderate values. A series of two surface renewal effects occur after this steep wave train in a region with low local slope values. Since no direct local correlation can be found the prove of a causal relationship between the steep wave train and the renewal effect is difficult. This is even more so since there are numerous boundary layer detachment effects without any detected steeper waves in the vicinity. On the other hand there are steep wave trains without any detectable surface renewal effects.

Figure 7.10: *Local boundary layer thickness plotted versus local wave slope. The measurements were done at a friction velocity of $u_* = 1.41$ cm/s in the channel at the UIUC. The plot shows no correlation between boundary layer thickness and wave slope on a local level for the channel at the UIUC. The fluctuations of the boundary layer thicknesses for a single wave slope is significant. The error bars denote the standard deviation from the mean value for a range of wave slopes of 0.04.*

Fig. 7.12 shows an image sequence where a steep wave seems to initiate a boundary layer detachment event. After this steep wave has passed an eddy structure can be seen in the concentration profile images.

Surface renewal is considered a statistical effect combining properties of different spatial and velocity scales – waves and turbulence. The effect of turbulent fields propagating with the flow velocity behind a wave train was introduced by (*Longuet-Higgins 1992*). The existence of burst phenomena was first qualitatively reported in this context by (*Ebuchi et al. 1993*). Considering the fact that the turbulence in the flow field remains stationary whereas the wave propagates with its phase velocity. This results in a statistical effect that is not locally correlated to wave slope.

A possibility for quantifying the above statements might be averaging of wave slope over a larger region. Mean square slope is the appropriate measure for averaging wave slopes. A correlation exists between mean square slope and transfer velocity for mass balance experiments ((*Jähne 1985*) and (*Jähne et al. 1985*)). However mass balance experiments are averaging over the complete water surface and a time span of several hours.

The averaging areas were chosen with a minimum size of $4\text{ mm} \times 2.3\text{ mm}$ and a maximum size

Figure 7.11: (A color plate of this figure can be found as fig. 9.5 on page 119) *Image sequence of the combined wave slope and concentration profile measurements at the UIUC ($u_* = 1.41$ cm/s). The thin stripes are wave slope measurements in long-wind direction conducted by Günther Balschbach. Local wave slope is coded in grey values. The concentration images were recorded at the same instant at the position marked with the black line in the slope images. The concentration images reveal that parts of the boundary layer are swept into the bulk. At this instance there is no direct correlation to local wave slope. On the other hand a series of steeper waves has passed this area before.*

Figure 7.12: (A color plate of this figure can be found as fig. 9.6 on page 120) *Image sequence of the combined wave slope and concentration profile measurements at the UIUC ($u_* = 1.47$ cm/s). Local wave slope is coded in grey values. The concentration images were recorded at the same instant at the position marked with the black line in the slope images. The concentration images reveal that parts of the boundary layer are swept into the bulk by a steep wave passing by. After the wave has passed a larger eddy structure transporting high concentration fluid into the bulk is revealed. The over-exposed parts in the second through fifth concentration image is an artifact caused by a total reflection of the tilted laser beam at the water surface.*

of $22.8 \text{ mm} \times 2.3 \text{ mm}$. The minimum size corresponds to the imaging area of the fluorescein experiments averaging over the cross-wind width of the wave slope image area-of-interest. The maximum size is almost the complete undistorted section of the wave slope image. The relative position of the averaging areas is shown in fig. 7.13. The position of the laser light sheet is again denoted by the black line in the center of the image.

Figure 7.13: Averaging areas for the calculation of mean square slope values from wave slope images. The averaging areas are marked with black rectangles and have the following sizes: area 1 $4 \times 2.3 \text{ mm}$, area 2 $11.4 \times 2.3 \text{ mm}$ and area 3 $22.8 \times 2.3 \text{ mm}$. The position of the laser light sheet is denoted by the black line in the center of the wave slope image.

The result of this procedure is shown in fig. 7.14. Again there is no correlation for any of the averaging areas. The mean boundary layer thickness values averaged over a range of 0.05 units are also shown. The length of the error bars was again chosen to be the standard deviation σ . For the two slope values at 0.85 and 0.95 the standard deviation was not defined and was considered infinite.

The results of this section show that there is no correlation on a local level between wave slope or mean square wave slope and boundary layer thickness. The result is not too surprising considering the fact that the phase speed of the waves is much different from the velocity of turbulent structures. A steep wave can experience micro-scale breaking and travel on at its phase speed. The turbulence induced into the water is much slower and might influence some other part of the water surface after the wave is long gone. Such an interpretation is consistent with theoretical examinations by (Longuet-Higgins 1992). Observations made by (Haußecker 1996) imaging the water surface with an infrared camera showed similar results. He could detect turbulent patches "left behind" by steep wave trains.

Figure 7.14: *Boundary layer thickness averaged over one image width (4 mm) plotted versus mean square slope averaged over 3 increasing areas. ($u_* = 1.41$ cm/s in the channel at the UIUC). The mean square slope was calculated from synchronous CISG measurements by Günther Balschbach. There is no correlation between boundary layer thickness and mean square slope for a single time step at this level.*

7.3 Comparison between a flat and a wavy interface

What is the difference in the mechanisms controlling gas transfer at a flat and at a wavy interface? Surface renewal effects can be seen for the flat as well as the wavy interface. On the other hand the mean profiles do change significantly in accordance with the predictions of the models. The surface renewal model predicts a change in the depth dependence of the surface renewal rate between a flat and a wavy interface. The surface renewal rate at a flat interface is depth dependent and the renewal rate is zero at the water surface. For a wavy water surface the surface renewal rate becomes independent of depth. This assumptions of the surface renewal rate is consistent with the observations made here. At a flat interface surface renewal effects never reached the water surface. The boundary layer thickness is not vanishing. On the other hand there are events for a wavy surface that completely deplete the boundary layer.

Looking at a single image from the previous sequence the averaged boundary layer thickness reveals that the boundary layer was almost completely swept into the bulk.

These observations agree with measurements by (*Asher and Pankow 1991*). They conducted experiments in a grid stirred tank also using a pH sensitive fluorescent dye. They did not measure concentration profiles but investigated the absorption of CO_2 into the surface layer of the solution.

Figure 7.15: (A color plate of this figure can be found as fig. 9.4 on page 118) *Left: Sequence of images recorded at the wind/wave facility of the UIUC with the wind coming from the right. The images were taken $1/180$ s apart at a friction velocity of $u_* = 1.5$ cm/s. The images are transferred into the frame of reference of the undulated water surface. The sequence shows a larger eddy sweeping through the boundary layer transporting high concentration fluid into the bulk. After the first eddy a second one can be seen. Both of these eddies reduce the boundary layer thickness down to almost nil.*

A second non-fluorescent dye was used to absorb all fluorescent light coming from the bulk. Only the fluorescent molecules in the surface layer were visible. They recorded time series of point measurements for different conditions. For the conditions of a clean interface they found peaks in their time series that they correlated to surface renewal effects. For an interface with a surfactant no such effects were reported directly at the interface.

Figure 7.16: Concentration image with a surface renewal effect. The plot shows the averaged local boundary layer thickness. The surface renewal effect brought forward a dramatic change in boundary layer thickness.

Chapter 8

Conclusions and Outlook

The experiments set up in this thesis showed for the first time two-dimensional time-resolved concentration fields within the aqueous mass boundary layer. The spatial and temporal resolutions are $20\ \mu\text{m}$ and 200 Hz respectively.

- Oxygen quenching experiments at a flat interface showed that the concentration fluctuations do not vanish at the water surface as do the velocity fluctuations. This is a contradiction to the assumptions of the small eddy model (*Coantic* 1986).
- Mean concentration profiles measured at wavy interfaces show a better correspondence with the predictions of the surface renewal model than with those of the small eddy model. Concentration decreases faster from the water surface into the bulk than predicted by the small eddy model.
- Experiments combining the laser induced fluorescence technique with synchronous wave slope measurements at the same location showed that there is no correlation between local wave slope and local boundary layer thickness. This contradicts predictions of a local correlation by (*Back and McCready* 1988).
- Bursting or surface renewal phenomena can be seen in the images. Single effects cannot be directly correlated to local features in the wave field. Nevertheless there is indication that steeper waves produce a turbulence wake that affects the boundary layer after the wave itself has already passed. This is consistent with theoretical examinations by (*Longuet-Higgins* 1992) and experimental results by (*Haußecker* 1996).
- The difference in gas exchange mechanisms between a wavy and a flat interface seem to lie in the penetration depth of surface renewal events. The measurements show that for a wavy interface the surface renewal events can penetrate up to the water surface. Although surface renewal is also seen for a flat interface penetration to the very surface is not observed

For technological reasons some of the above observations were only possible at a single wind/wave facility. Verification of the above results in different wind/wave facilities remains necessary.

Future experiments should focus on a better resolution and understanding of the 3-dimensional structure of turbulence effects. A 2-dimensional light-sheet technique cannot completely reveal the spatial structures of turbulent eddies. Small circulation cells with their rotational axis in wind direction were reported by (*Haußecker 1996*). Expanding the current setup into a true volume visualization technique can reveal the nature of these Langmuir-like structures and their influence on gas exchange.

Improving the image processing tools for image sequence analysis can enhance the understanding of surface renewal effects. At this point bursting phenomena can only be qualitatively observed. With sophisticated image sequence analysis tools a tracking and quantification of single effects seems possible.

Statistics of burst effects in the turbulent boundary layer were calculated by (*Rao et al. 1971*). These results were applied to surface temperatures by (*Haußecker 1996*). He showed that the shape of the probability function gives a measure for the relevant renewal time constants. An analogue method is applicable to boundary layer thickness statistics that might yield another way of determining the transfer velocity and evaluating model assumptions.

Chapter 9

Color plates

Figure 9.1: (Color plate of fig. 4.23 on page 67) *View on the setup at the circular wind/wave facility at the University of Heidelberg. The top part of the picture shows the laser optics mount with the scanner. The bottom part shows the f-theta lens in its mount which also holds the scanner mirror of the wave follower. The tilted window can be seen in the red frame.*

Figure 9.2: (Color plate of fig. 4.6 on page 49) *Experimental setup for the first set of experiments at the wind/wave facility of the Department of Chemical Engineering at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign. The pictures show a side view of the imaging optics and a frontal view with the imaging optics (left) and the laser light sheet (right).*

Figure 9.3: (Color plate of fig. 7.5 on page 99) *Left: Space time image of oxygen concentration profiles of an oxygen invasion experiment at a flat interface with $u_* = 0.63$ cm/s. The aqueous mass boundary layer can be seen as a blue layer in the top part of the image. The image is converted to the frame of reference of the water surface. Right: Cross section through a single concentration profile at time $t = 8$ s.*

Figure 9.4: (Color plate of fig. 7.15 on page 110) *Left: Sequence of images recorded at the wind/wave facility of the UIUC with the wind coming from the right. The images were taken $1/180$ s apart at a friction velocity of $u_* = 1.5$ cm/s. The images are transferred into the frame of reference of the undulated water surface. The sequence shows two larger eddies sweeping through the boundary layer transporting high concentration fluid into the bulk. After the first eddy a second one can be seen. Both of these eddies reduce the boundary layer thickness down to almost nil.*

Figure 9.5: (Color plate of fig. 7.11 on page 106) *Image sequence of the combined wave slope and concentration profile measurements at the UIUC ($u_* = 1.41$ cm/s). The stripes are wave slope measurements conducted by Günther Balschbach. Local wave slope is color coded. The concentration images were recorded at the same instant at the position marked with the black line in the slope images. Concentration is also displayed in pseudo colors. The concentration images reveal that parts of the boundary layer are swept into the bulk. At this instance there is no direct correlation to local wave slope. On the other hand a series of steeper waves has passed this area before.*

Figure 9.6: (Color plate of fig. 7.12 on page 107) *Image sequence of the combined wave slope and concentration profile measurements at the UIUC ($u_* = 1.47$ cm/s). Local wave slope is coded in grey values. The concentration images were recorded at the same instant at the position marked with the black line in the slope images. The concentration images reveal that parts of the boundary layer are swept into the bulk by a steep wave passing by. After the wave has passed a larger eddy structure transporting high concentration fluid into the bulk is revealed. The over-exposed parts in the second through fifth concentration image is an artifact caused by a total reflection of the tilted laser beam at the water surface.*

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Appendix A

Fluorescence

A.1 Photo-physical processes

Electron transfer in laser induced fluorescence processes can in general be described by the so called Einstein coefficients for the transition from ground state to excited state and vice versa. If the electron densities in the ground and excited state are N_g and N_e , respectively

$$\frac{dN_e(t)}{dt} = N_g(t)(B_{g \rightarrow e}I_\nu) - N_e(t)(Q_{e \rightarrow g} + B_{e \rightarrow g}I_\nu + A_{e \rightarrow g} + A_{ion} + P_e) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $B_{g \rightarrow e}$ and $B_{e \rightarrow g}$ are the Einstein coefficients for the transitions from the ground into the excited state and back. $Q_{e \rightarrow g}$ is the loss of excited electrons by collision quenching, A_{ion} the loss of electrons by ionization, e.g. multi-photon excitation which can usually be neglected. P_e stands for the pre-dissociation term which can also be neglected in most cases. Finally the term $A_{e \rightarrow g}$ describes the fluorescence transition from the excited state back to the ground state. This is the value of interest in laser induced fluorescence. Neglecting the terms A_{ion} and P_e and keeping the total number of electrons constant (i.e. $N_g + N_e = \text{const}$) we get an expression for the fluorescence rate R_f :

$$R_f = A_{e \rightarrow g}N_e(t \gg \tau) = N_g B_{g \rightarrow e} I_\nu \left(\frac{A_{e \rightarrow g}}{A_{e \rightarrow g} + Q_{e \rightarrow g}} \right) \left(\frac{1}{1 + I_\nu / I_\nu^{sat}} \right) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where I_ν^{sat} is the saturation intensity of the laser beam. This equation holds true for times t that are significantly bigger than a molecular time constant τ . If $I_\nu \ll I_\nu^{sat}$ which is the case for both experimental setups here fluorescence becomes a linear function of the incident laser intensity I_ν :

$$R_f = N_g B_{g \rightarrow e} I_\nu \left(\frac{A_{e \rightarrow g}}{A_{e \rightarrow g} + Q_{e \rightarrow g}} \right) \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Figure A.1 shows a simplified view of the most important photo-physical processes with their typical lifetimes τ (Krasovitskii and Bolotin 1988 and Schaefer 1977).

Figure A.1: *Simplified term scheme with the most important photo-physical processes. The abbreviations mean: IC = internal conversion and ISC = intersystem crossing. The straight lines mean a photon emitting or absorbing process, the saw-tooth line stands for a non-radiative conversion. (after Mayer and Neuenhofer 1994).*

An electron is lifted to the excited state by absorption of a photon. In a solution the transition from ground to excited state by light absorption is fast compared to the dipolar relaxation with the solvent molecules. Hence the dye molecule finds itself in a non-equilibrium Franck-Condon state following light absorption, and it relaxes to an excited equilibrium state within about 10^{-14} to 10^{-12} s. Similarly, the return to the equilibrium ground state is also via a Franck-Condon state, followed by dipolar relaxation. An establishment of the protolytic equilibrium as stated in section 3.1.3 has to take place in the time span of the fluorescence lifetime. The same is true for a possible quenching effect by external quenchers like oxygen. Quenching is that effective for pyrene butyric acid (PBA) because the lifetime of the S_1 state for PBA with 100 to 205 ns is extremely large (Vaughan and Weber (1970)). In contrast to that the lifetime of fluorescein fluorescence is given by (Kessel 1936) with 4.3 ns.

A very effective process to decrease luminescence lifetime and intensity is quenching. Lifetime is decreased in the presence of other molecules which are called quenchers. Several physical mechanisms exist for luminescence quenching (cf. Engler *et al.* 1992):

- Electron transfer. Molecules in their excited states are much better electron donors and

acceptors of electrons. Their ionization potential decreases and electron affinity increases by a value of excitation energy. Quenching occurs at distances equal to or slightly more than molecular radii. The rate constants are diffusion limited if the reaction is exothermic and smaller if the reaction is endothermic. Such a process is of course only possible if the lifetime of the excited molecule is comparable or bigger than the time needed for establishment of the protolytic equilibrium Förster 1950. Guyot *et al.* 1975 could show that this is not the case for fluorescein. Figure A.2 shows this luminescence quenching mechanism. The electron transfer ionization potential I_{M^*} of a molecule M^* in the excited state is lower than in the ground state: $I_{M^*} = I_M - E_{0,0}$, and electron transfer to an acceptor molecule, which is endothermic in the ground state, exothermic in the excited state.

- Energy transfer (dipole-dipole energy transfer, resonance quenching, Förster mechanism). The fluorescence spectrum of the luminophore overlaps the absorption spectrum of the quencher. Such a type of quenching may occur at a distance of 5 to 10 nm. In fluids the quenching rate constants are higher than diffusion limited. For quenching of the majority of luminophores by oxygen this process is insignificant.
- Induced energy transfer (see figure A.3) (spin or energy exchange mechanism). Radiationless singlet-triplet conversion may be induced by quenchers which contain heavy atoms (with atomic mass more than 30 a.u., such as most halogen atoms or ions) or unpaired electrons, as free radicals, molecules in a triplet state, like oxygen.

The lifetime of an excited molecule in the absence of a quencher may be expressed as:

$$\tau = \frac{1}{k_f + k_d} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where k_f is the rate of light emission and k_d is the sum of rates of radiationless deactivation, i.e. of internal conversion and intersystem crossing. In the presence of a certain concentration c of quenchers the lifetime of excited molecule is described by the Stern-Volmer equation:

$$\frac{\tau_0}{\tau} = 1 + Kc \quad (\text{A.5})$$

where K is the so called quenching constant.

A.2 Experimental setup for the absorption measurements

Fig. A.4 shows the experimental setup used to measure the absorption coefficients for fluorescein solutions. The setup is described in detail in (Münsterer 1993). The solution was illuminated with a xenon arc lamp and the desired wavelength was filtered out with an interference filter. The absorption profiles in the solution were imaged with a CCD camera. Time sequences of the

Figure A.2: *Electron transfer scheme. (from Engler et al. 1992)*

absorption profiles were recorded while a titration of the solution was going on. The readout from a pH probe was recorded at the same time with the imaged profiles. The advantage of this setup is the possibility of getting an almost continuous record of absorption and fluorescence values vs. pH value. One disadvantage is that re-absorption effects cannot be accounted for. The other problem is that the response time of the pH probe is critical for the success of this method and pH resolution is limited to the accuracy of the pH probe used.

A.3 Fluorescence intensity measurements

Fig. A.5 shows the setup for the measurements of fluorescence intensity vs. pH value. Fluorescence was excited by an argon ion laser in an opaque tank with a 10^{-5} M fluorescein solution. The fluorescence was imaged by a similar setup to the one used for the combined PBA/fluorescein experiments at the channel of the University of Heidelberg. The CCD camera imaged the fluorescence profile through a side window in the test tank. The laser beam was positioned approx. 2 mm from the tank wall to avoid an excess of re-absorption in the solution. A tube with a window on either side

Figure A.3: Induced energy transfer which is the significant transfer process for the oxygen quenching mechanism. (from Engler et al. 1992)

was positioned outside the tank and in the optical path of the imaging optics. The tube was filled with a 2×10^{-5} M fluorescein solution. This re-absorption section was 7 cm long. The test tank was filled with 10^{-5} M solutions with pH 9, pH 6.88, pH 6 and pH 5 respectively. The pH value of the

Figure A.4: Setup for the absorption measurements with fluorescein solution. The solution was illuminated using a xenon arc lamp and an interference filter. Fluorescence was detected with a standard CCD camera. (from (Münsterer 1993))

re-absorption section was kept constant. This produced a comparable effect to the one visualizing the aqueous mass boundary layer in a wind/wave channel. The local pH value in the boundary layer is changed but the pH value of the re-absorption body, i.e. the solution bulk remains the same.

The maximum errors for this experiment were estimated as follows. A 5% error in establishing the used solution concentration seems reasonable. The solutions were established by dilution of a common stock solution. The relative laser intensity fluctuations were below 1.5%. High frequency laser power noise was reduced by averaging over a sequence of 1800 images recorded in 12s. An additional source of error is the position of the water surface that was moving a few pixels, i.e. a few 16 microns between successive frames. Adding up all these errors the maximum error should be well below 10%. Since only relative errors between the measurements with different pH values go into the calculations the errors should be even lower than that.

The setup used here was used because an original setup using a spectroscopy cuvette with a fluorescein solution did fail. The reason was that fluorescein solution is bleached by the laser beam very rapidly. In such a cuvette almost no convective currents are present. Therefore the fluorescein molecules were exposed to the laser beam relatively long. The effect was that the detected fluorescence intensity decreased by a factor of 2 within seconds. This seems to be a problem also in measurements in the big wind/wave channel. If the intensity of the laser beam gets to high

Figure A.5: *Setup for the re-absorption intensity calibration measurements with fluorescein solution. The solution was illuminated using a focussed argon ion laser. Fluorescence was detected with a standard CCD camera.*

photo-bleaching effects can be detected at the turning points of the scanned laser light sheet.

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